

**COMMUNICATING PUBLIC POLICY: THE CASE OF ORDINANCE IN THE CITY
OF METRO MANILA**

MELINDA M. DOCALLOS

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Melinda M. Docallos

**COMMUNICATING PUBLIC POLICY: THE CASE OF ORDINANCE IN THE CITY
OF METRO MANILA**

Thesis Adviser:

MELINDA BANDALARIA, Ph.D.
Faculty of Information and Communication Studies

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Acceptance Page:

This paper prepared by **MELINDA M. DOCALLOS** with the title: **“COMMUNICATING PUBLIC POLICY: THE CASE OF ORDINANCE IN THE CITY OF METRO MANILA”**. is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Program.

MELINDA DELA PEÑA BANDALARIA, Ph.D.
Chair, Thesis Committee

Date

BENJAMINA PAULA G. FLOR, Ph.D.
Member, Thesis Committee

Date

JOANE V. SERRANO, Ph.D.
Member, Thesis Committee

Date

DR. ALEXANDER G. FLOR, Ph.D.
Dean
Faculty of Information and Communication Studies

Date

BIOGRAPHICAL SKETCH

The author, Melinda Madrid Docallos, is from Iligan City, Lanao Del Norte. She's the 6th child of Aurelio L. Madrid and Erlinda B. Madrid. She's married to Richard G. Docallos with two (2) children, Raphael Brian Docallos and Reginal Bernice Docallos.

She finished a degree in Bachelor of Science in Management in 1995 at Mindanao State University – Iligan Institute of Technology. She worked while in college to support her educational needs as her way to lighten then the burden of her parents being the 6th of the ten (10) children. She likewise earned a Diploma in Urban and Regional Planning at the University of the Philippines – Diliman on 16 April 2000.

She currently holds the position of Head Executive Assistant at the Bases Conversion and Development Authority (BCDA). She used to be the head of the Secretariat of the Bids and Awards Committee for Consulting Services, and Special Bids and Awards Committees of BCDA. She is currently the head of the Secretariat of Bids and Awards Committee for Infrastructure Projects.

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DEDICATION

First and foremost, I dedicate my dissertation work to God who continuously guides me not only in this endeavor but also in every day of my life. I also dedicate this to my husband who has been my buddy since day one of my journey in my master's degree, which I might not have been able to complete without his unfailing love and support. I dedicate this as well to my children, Raphael Brian M. Docallos and Regina Bernice M. Docallos, who have always been my sources of strength and motivation to keep dreaming and achieving my goals.

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to alleviate the widespread case of Internet addiction caused by the proliferation of Internet cafés or computer gaming shops, which is a common dilemma of parents residing in one of the cities in Metro Manila (hereinafter referred to as the “City” for this study). It is noteworthy that the officials of the City have passed a resolution (hereinafter referred to as the “City Ordinance” in this study) to regulate Internet café operations in the City. However, there is a need to address whether the City Ordinance has indeed served its purpose as deemed by this study.

Responses obtained from Internet café users in this study confirmed that excessive visits to computer shops are common among young children in the City. These responses were corroborated with the results of the survey conducted among parents. Both results confirmed that there is an Internet café–related problem among the youth in the City that threatens their good education and bright future. Furthermore, these results suggested that the implementation of and information dissemination done for the City Ordinance, if any, were ineffective.

Given the importance of communication in the success of any public policy, and the changing information environment, the above premise suggests that the very essence of this study—that is, the method used in the dissemination and campaign of the City Ordinance—was examined.

Chapter I

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Public policy is defined by Ikelegbe (2006) as a suggested action by the government to achieve some desired aims or objectives, as well as the political leaders' initiatives for the betterment of the community. According to Parth J Shah of the Centre for Civil Society (2011), the several branches of government, as well as the court, make public policy. Policies can be viewed as the "rules of the game" in everyday life, influencing the choices people make in pursuit of their goals, and so influencing the overall and unintentional repercussions of everyone's activities.

Moreover, public policy is often the response of political leaders to social issues within the community. In light of a specific social situation, public policy guides and determines existing and future public decisions, as well as the institutional acts, decisions, or behaviors of the private individual or private enterprise. In essence, it governs the activities of government and commercial institutions in providing services aimed at solving a certain problem, according to Ugwuanyi et al. (2013). However, individual interpretation plays a significant role in policy transmission and understanding, and individuals at different levels of the system might perceive the policy in dramatically different ways even though it is stated and presented in the same manner repeatedly.

Much research have suggested that problems in program implementation were major sources of poor government performance. These issues ranged from inadequate coordination between agencies and ranks to the lack of cooperation from frontline workers who disagree with the program and implement it with less

enthusiasm. Frequently, program targets fail to act in the way program designers intend to. Furthermore, compliance with government policies varies in each case, and in some cases, it is hardly observed.

The Oxford English Dictionary defines compliance as "acting under or yielding to a desire, request, condition, etc." Compliance may or may not imply consent to behave in a specific manner. Hence, begrudging it is considered as such.

The government may use incentives to get the desired compliance for policies from the public. Governments may also restrict, regulate, or mandate specific behaviors, with penalties for failure to comply. There is no single, universal response to the question, "What is a compliance problem?" Richard Thaler and Cass Sunstein (2008) argued that program targets have limited information processing ability, and that biases embedded into predictions of payoffs from alternative choices may lead them to make suboptimal decisions for their own or society's sake. Thus, communicating policy compliance is an important stage in the implementation of any program.

Policy communication is frequently underestimated, despite its importance in policy creation and execution. This can take numerous forms, including written laws and regulations, memoranda, or group communication. Whatever the case, communicating public policy, specifically its compliance, must be given utmost attention during the implementation stage if it aims to address societal problems for the betterment of the community.

The City Ordinance

There are many forms of societal problems and in order to address them, the government is constantly observed developing policies in reaction to these challenges and as the government's initiative for the economic growth, national development, and citizen well-being. The government's formulation of policy to address these problems is necessary, otherwise, they may devolve into unmanageable stages that undermine society's socioeconomic growth and development according to Okoli & Onah, 2002.

In the City, the councilors acknowledged that the operation and growth of Internet establishments in the country have been inadequately regulated and controlled, resulting in the rise of Internet-related problems. The City Councilors had passed the City Ordinance as a response and preventive measure to pornography and other related problems brought about by the proliferation of Internet café businesses. It was also passed to regulate the establishment and operation of Internet cafés or computer rental and gaming shops or centers in the City. The councilors have also acknowledged that excessive computer gaming can jeopardize the academic performance of students. The third clause of the City Ordinance states that:

“WHEREAS, there is an urgent need to regulate and check the entry of minors/students to Internet cafés or computer rental shops/computer gaming shops or centers as excessive playing or entertainment therein especially during school hours is an unnecessary distraction that can jeopardize their academic performance and advancement.”

Section 7 of the City Ordinance provides some prohibitions inside Internet cafés / computer rental shops, to wit:

1. *Surf the Internet for websites containing pornographic or lewd materials, satanic/violent materials, or those that advertise or promote prostitution.*
2. *Use, consume, or trade prohibited drugs and intoxicating liquor/beverages within the premises.*
3. *Gamble online and/or bet among customers inside the premises.*
4. *In the case of students of minor age, the following are prohibited:*
 - a. *Entering the premises wearing school uniform (except students who are doing research/school work in Internet cafés or computer rental shops during vacant/free school hours)*
 - b. *Entering the premises during school hours (except students who will be doing research/school work in Internet cafés or computer rental shops during vacant/free school hours). Computer gaming shops or centers are strictly prohibited from admitting students during school hours.*
 - c. *Entering the premises without any credible identification (ID) card and official class schedule duly issued and certified by the Registrar's Office*

5. *For both students and out-of-school youths of minor age, enter into the premises during curfew hours, which starts at 10:00 PM and ends at 4:00 AM.*

Similarly, Section 8 of the City Ordinance provides that the owners/proprietors/managers of Internet cafés or computer rental/gaming shops or centers are required to observe the following measures in their operation:

1. Ensure strict customer compliance with Section 7 of the City Ordinance. IDs of all customers and class schedules of students (minors) must be checked as a basis for allowing them to enter the premises and identifying Internet users for monitoring content viewed and for crime-prevention purposes.
2. Display necessary warning signs against access to pornographic and online gambling sites, such as "INTERNET PORNOGRAPHY AND ONLINE GAMBLING ARE PROHIBITED."
3. Install filtering software to block or deny access to all pornographic and online gambling sites.

The Adverse Effect of New Technology

The internet connects individuals all over the world, giving a wealth of knowledge, communication, and entertainment. However, as technology advances, contemporary society is bombarded with problems that mostly affect the lives of the youth, such as, but not limited to, video and online game addiction, Internet pornography, and illicit affairs online. The Internet's popularity has had an impact on every element of human life. The rise of online games, in particular, has transformed traditional video gaming, and engagement in the activity has grown increasingly

popular as a form of leisure, particularly among teens. While some people play these games in a healthy manner, according to Grusser & Thalemann (2007), epidemiological research revealed that other people acquired excessive use and symptoms associated with substance-related addiction. The addiction to Internet gaming has been regarded as similar to the addictions caused by substance abuse, supporting the premise that it is a true addiction, although it is related to behavior like the addiction to gambling (Grusser & Thalemann, 2007). Griffiths (2013) defined addictive behavior as any behavior characterized by the six main components of addiction: salience, mood modulation, tolerance, withdrawal symptoms, conflict, and relapse.

According to the researchers (e.g., May, 1994; Griffiths & Hunt, 1998; Greenberg, Lewis & Dodd, 1999; Salguero & Moran, 2002; Anderson & Bushman, 2001), most computer gaming research has focused on teens. This study has concentrated on the negative effects or repercussions, such as excessive play and addiction, violence, and other physical and psychosocial effects discussed below. According to these researchers, the research on excessive computer gaming among adolescents and young adults has gained increased public attention in a number of nations. For example, internet addiction has become a major societal issue among Chinese youths according to Wu and Zhu (2004). According to them, 10.6% of the Chinese college students was identified as addicted to the internet. Internet usage appears to be affecting patients worldwide as well (Freeman, 2008). The detrimental effects of Internet gaming addiction have caused governments and health-care providers in Southeast Asian countries to recognize the gravity of the situation and develop a number of initiatives to curb and ameliorate the problem. Internet game addiction is seen as a major public health concern in South Korea, with up to 24% of

youngsters diagnosed with it and hospitalized. Following a research by the Ministry of Education, the Japanese government identified the problem, which led to the construction of fasting camps where persons suffering from Internet and game addiction were assisted by cutting them off from technology totally. In response to the increasing concern on internet game addiction, treatment centers and programs specially created and dedicated to the address this concern have been established in Europe, which includes the outpatient clinics for behavioral addictions in Mainz, Germany, and the Catio Nightingale Hospital in London, UK) and the United States, which includes the centers for inpatient for the RESTART Internet Addiction Recovery Program in Seattle and the digital detoxification and recovery center in Pennsylvania), which signaled that the need for professional assistance is increasing. Internet Gaming Disorder is a condition that physicians and researchers must take into account, according to The American Psychiatric Association. According to Kuss, 2013, internet gaming disorder was first featured in the appendix of the updated version of the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders in June 2013.

In one study, data was gathered from several online gaming communities where people offered or shared their thoughts on the subject. The research of different online gamers' experience revealed that to be indulged in internet games has far-reaching ramifications in the individuals' lives. According to Chappell, Eatough, Davies & Griffiths, 2006, the consequences ranged from frequent absence from school and missing work to losing one's job and/or spouse, family, and friends.

Negative Consequences

Internet gaming addiction has evolved into a major global mental health problem as it caused impairments in various behavioral aspects of addicts, including interactions with others and academic performance according to Scherer (1997; Morahan-Martin & Schumacher (2000); and Dong et al. (2010). The concern appears to be supported by an increasing number of studies linking Internet gaming addiction to a variety of harmful outcomes. Various studies' findings have emphasized the detrimental repercussions of Internet gaming addiction. According to various researchers (Allison et al., 2006; Chan & Rabinowitz, 2006; Batthyany et al., 2009; Chiu et al., 2004; Skoric et al., 2009; Jeong & Kin, 2010; Rehbein et al., 2010; Dworak et al., 2007; Griffiths et al., 2004; Yee, 2006; Peters & Malesky, 2008; King & Delfabbro, 2009; Liu & Peng, 2009; Peng & Liu, 2010; Hussain & Griffiths, 2009; Lemmens et al., 2011) these include psychosocial issues such as gaming obsession, a lack of real-life relationships, inattention, aggressive/oppositional behavior and hostility, stress, decreased academic achievement, a decline in verbal memory performance, sacrificing hobbies, sleep, work, education, socialization, time with partner/family, as well as associated problems such as dissociation, lower psychosocial well-being and loneliness, maladaptive cognitions, and increased suicidal thoughts. Furthermore, according to the researchers (Batthyany et al., 2009; Chuang, 2006; Allison et al., 2006; and Dworak et al., 2007), psychosomatic issues were discovered to be side effects of Internet gaming addiction. These included psychosomatic issues, seizures, and sleep disorders. The rather broad list of possible adverse effects suggests unequivocally that Internet gaming addiction is a real phenomena that should be taken seriously, and therefore demands greater attention.

Stories, Reports, and Articles

Internet addiction might yet to be acknowledged as a serious mental disorder, but various stories, reports, and articles about computer gaming addiction and Internet gaming disorder have been heard and read for years, and some patients have sought professional help to get rid of the addiction. In one of the featured articles of The Sydney Morning Herald (published online on 7 December 2007) entitled, "Computer Addiction 'a growing problem', Australian clinical psychologist, media commentator, and writer Sally-Anne McCormack estimated that 50% of her customers suffered from internet addiction, with some staying up until 4:00 a.m. to fuel their addiction. She said that some clients spent longer hours on the computer in a day like 16 hours or more, and some have dropped out of school. Many of these people, according to McCormack, had Asperger's Syndrome, a form of autism characterized by social isolation and quirky conduct, and was an outcome of computer addiction.

In China, an internet addict is defined as someone who uses the internet for non-school-related activities for more than six hours per day, according to filmmakers Shosh Shlam and Hilla Medalia (The Mirror—UK tabloid newspaper, 7 July 2015 online publication).

In the United States, medical practitioners and health officials have been worried about internet addiction that made them saw the need for rehabilitation and treatment centers for those having internet-related disorders, and considered the phenomenon as more serious than a simple societal problem, (CNN, 2015). Furthermore, Neurological complications, psychological disturbances, and social problems are the conditions that can be caused by Internet Addiction Disorder (IAD),

thus IAD can ruin lives according to a 2012 article published in *Current Psychiatry Reviews* (pp. 292-298).

The Philippines is not isolated from Internet/computer-related issues. ABS-CBN News once featured a son who stopped schooling and spent more time on the computer. The man showed signs of computer addiction according to a Filipino clinical psychologist and psychiatrist, who also said that computer addiction works like illegal drugs as it causes a person to become antisocial.

Dr. Randy Dellosa, a psychiatrist and computer addiction expert, stated in a 28 November 2010 online article of PhilStar that computer addiction can cause serious societal issues and health conditions such as mood swings, withdrawal from family and friends, sleep deprivation, poor eating habits and hygiene, wrist injury, back and neck pains, stealing, lying, poor attention span in school or at work, absenteeism and tardiness, poor performance in school, and relationship breakdown.

Reports and stories of Internet/computer-related problems also revealed that entertainment caused by new technology could ruin people's lives, especially the younger ones if used excessively and authorities do not act on the problem.

In the City, there were no documented cases of absenteeism and school dropouts caused by gaming addiction or any computer-related problems based on records of authorities, but this does not mean that such problems do not exist. Internet- or computer-related problems could be present everywhere. However, according to some sociologists, before a social problem can be recognized, the public or a segment of it must first view the circumstance as a problem (Lauer, 1976,

p. 125). This would imply that the presence of societal problems is only recognized when an objective condition exists and the people or public characterize it as problematic. In other words, social issues exist only when people believe they do. If no one perceives a certain societal issue to be problematic, it does not exist. However, sociologists have also said that undesirable conditions and behaviors, remarkable or not, should be regarded as social concerns.

Often, social problems require swift government actions to alleviate, if not ultimately eradicate, the problems to achieve social change. Parth J Shah (2011), the Centre for Civil Society's founding president, claimed that public policy was the most effective vehicle towards achieving large and long-term social reform.

Statement of the Problem

According to Anderson (1984), public policy is a deliberate course of action taken by an actor or a group of actors to address an issue or matter of concern. Stewart, Hedge, and Lester (2008) on the other hand described public policy as a sequence or pattern of government operations or decisions aimed at resolving societal issues. Many scholars have defined public policy from diverse perspectives, but they were all directed toward the same goal—that is, to contribute to the betterment of society. While public policy is formulated for the common good, failure of implementation should not be an option.

Many issues surround the success of public policy. Some scholars (Bovens et al., 2001, O'Neill & Primus, 2005, Pollack, 2007) have mentioned nonfailure, mixed success, and partial success. However these are ad hoc terms used to describe

individual occurrences and are not positioned within a broader framework that can reflect the diversity of results created by the policies.

According to McConnell, (2010), a policy is successful if the desired objectives set by the proponents were met or achieved, has no significant criticism, and has widespread support, and it is considered a failure if these conditions are not met. Policymaking success indicates that the government has lawfully implemented the desired policy in favor of the coalition's interests. However, the success of policy during the process stage does not guarantee success a success of policy at the program stage. Policymaking should entail adequate checks and balances because without going through this process, it would be prone to flaws as the set goals or objective and/or instruments were not refined to produce viable policies through incremental bargaining, deliberate engagement, partisan and plurality, and careful policy design, according to the scholars (Lindblom, 1965; Braybrooke and Lindblom, 1970; Carson and Martin, 1999; Gutmann and Thompson, 2004; Crick, 1993; Stoker, 2006; Schneider & Ingram, 1997). The said outcome would be similar to the government winning the battle (process) and losing the war (program).

Furthermore, the success of public policy is contingent on the success of its implementation. Even the best policies will fail if they are not executed successfully and correctly. Implementation studies focused on understanding the success or failure of public policy by delving into the elements that influence it. This idea of implementation drew policymakers' and enforcers' attention to the processes that influenced and determined the policy's outcome, according to Bempah (2012).

Information dissemination strategies also play a big role in the implementation and success of public policy. The application of communication theory in public

policy analysis by Goggin et al. (1990) focused on the transmission of the policy's message across many levels of the system. The people involved in the implementation of a policy or program must have adequate information for it to be successful, including technical knowledge on the subject as well as levels and patterns of communication amongst actors. An essential element of the successful implementation of public policy is an effective communication between the government and its people, according to Ahn, (2012).

The Sangguniang Panlungsod of the City enacted the City Ordinance as its response to the rise of Internet-related problems with an emphasis on the protection of the welfare of minors. However, it has been observed that Internet café operators and their customers have not behaved consistently with the objectives of the City Ordinance. Given the vital role of communication in the success of policy and the importance of the City Ordinance to the alleviation and/or eradication of Internet-related problems in the City, an examination of the information dissemination process of this regulation was warranted.

Objectives of the Study

Internet-related problems are common among parents whose children frequently visit Internet cafés, and fortunately, the City Ordinance was enacted to regulate the establishment and operation of computer shops in the City. However, there is a need to identify whether the City Ordinance was properly or effectively communicated to the citizens and observe whether they have behaved or have not behaved according to its provisions. Thus, the objectives of this study are:

1. To determine and describe the level of awareness of Internet café operators of the City Ordinance;
2. To determine and describe the level of compliance/implementation of the City Ordinance by Internet café operators in the City;
3. To examine and describe how the City Ordinance was communicated to the citizens, especially to Internet café operators;
4. To establish whether Internet-related problems do exist in the City to support the worth of the study; and
5. To provide recommendations for the sustained adoption of desired behaviors, i.e., full compliance and implementation of Internet café operators under the City Ordinance.

How the City Ordinance was communicated could be a contributing factor to how Internet café operators and users behaved. Whether or not it was communicated effectively might be cause for the existence of Internet-related problems in the City. Furthermore, the dissemination process of the City Ordinance would have had repercussions in the Internet café-related problems in the City, i.e., these problems were lessened or eradicated or might have worsened.

Research Questions

To further satisfy the objectives of this study, the researcher aims to gain an in-depth understanding of how Internet café operators and their customers behaved or not according to the objectives of the City Ordinance, and establish whether their behavior correlates with their knowledge of the City Ordinance. This study was guided by the following questions:

1. To what extent was the City Ordinance implemented by the Internet café operators inside their Internet cafés?
2. How knowledgeable are Internet café operators in the City about the City Ordinance?
3. How did Internet café users behave inside the Internet cafés vis-à-vis the objectives of the City Ordinance?
4. What were the experiences/problems encountered by the parents of children frequenting Internet cafés?
5. What were the strategies used by barangay officials, if any, in the dissemination of the City Ordinance, and how was the City Ordinance communicated to the Internet café operators?

Hypotheses of the Study

1. The City Ordinance has not been stringently implemented and clearly communicated, especially to the Internet Café operators in the City.
2. The Internet Café operators are not strictly implementing the City Ordinance in their Internet Cafés or computer shops due to lack of knowledge of this Ordinance and lack of enforcement from the authorities.
3. The students who frequent the Internet Cafés/computer shops and spend long hours for gaming have frequent absences from their classes.

Significance of the Study

“If we are to reach real peace in this world... we shall have to begin with the children.” — Mahatma Gandhi

It is often said that the youth are the leaders of tomorrow, even if, in reality, some are already leading important changes today. They are heralded as individuals who have the power to change the world. However, the advent of technologies, such as the Internet and other networks, confront the future of young people as it may destroy their lives if ignored.

Internet-related problems among the youth mostly include absenteeism and school drop-outs resulting in poor education, which might have been caused by Internet-related activities, such as computer/online gaming. Thus, it is the ultimate goal of this study to alleviate and eradicate gradually the Internet-related problems in the City brought about by the proliferation of Internet cafés. Although the study merely uncovered and described how the City Ordinance was disseminated to and how it affected the behaviors of Internet café operators, the findings could lead to the realization among the citizens, especially political leaders, that the City Ordinance should be working and must be effective in its intended purpose. The City Ordinance was commendable for emphasizing the protection of students' welfare, especially that of minors, but the City Officials do not seem to take the matter seriously. Hence, this study hopes to draw the attention of the City Officials and make them realize that there has been no sufficient information dissemination done on the City Ordinance, and there is a need to reevaluate or revisit its implementation. With this, commitment and adequate financial support should hopefully be granted if needed. Furthermore, implementation can be viewed as a process, an output, and an outcome. It is the process of interactions between goal-setting and the actions directed toward achieving them, according to Pressman & Wildavsky (1973). An evaluation of the process, output, and outcome could lead to the stringent implementation of the City

Ordinance, and, subsequently, the full attainment of the desired behavior. The attainment of desired behavior could increase school attendance and improvement of academic achievement among students, especially the younger. This could also lessen social challenges in the City, such as family instability, poor education, unemployment, and Internet-related crimes.

This study also aims to promote awareness among parents that there is a City Ordinance that regulates the establishment and operation of Internet cafés. Their awareness could also create a positive effect on the behaviors of operators and users. Knowing the City Ordinance, parents can help police encourage the Internet café operators to strictly comply with the regulations.

In addition, this study could help government officials in other cities or places realize that a city ordinance must be enacted or reevaluated if a similar resolution already exists in their respective areas.

Finally, this study could provide insights to policymakers and other government officials in the formulation of policies and laws and their effective communication/dissemination and implementation.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

This study uncovered the information dissemination done on City Ordinance, particularly how the City authorities communicated this City Ordinance to the Internet Café Operators. This was done through a short interview with the City Officials and the surveys conducted with the Internet café users and owners/operators at District 2 in the City.

The Internet Cafés mostly operated from 1:00 PM to 1:00 AM but the data collection was done from 2:00 PM to 7:00 PM because it has been observed that the influx of Internet café users in the Internet Cafe is during this period, and the safety of the researcher was also considered. Thus, another limitation of this study was that the activities inside the Internet cafés beyond 7:00 PM have not been covered.

Another limitation of this study would be that the responses of the Internet café users might not have been accurate. During the survey, it was observed that Internet café users were too focused on their games on the computer, making them answer the survey so quickly.

Operational Definition of Terminologies

Public Policy – is a guide to action that links to a larger framework and entails putting into action a philosophy, concept, vision, and choice that will be translated into numerous programs, projects, and activities. It is a framework for government intervention that encompasses a variety of activities. Public policy is also described as a deliberate course of action taken by an actor or group of actors in response to an issue or matter of concern. Furthermore, it is a sequence or pattern of government actions or decisions intended to address certain socioeconomic issues.

Communication – It is the process through which a sender and a receiver communicate on a certain message under specific conditions in order to establish a mutual agreement. (Schramm, 1954).

Participatory Communication – This has been defined as “a dynamic, interactional, and transformative process of dialogue between people, groups, and

institutions that enables people, both individually and collectively, to realize their full potential and be engaged in their own welfare” (Singhal, 2001).

City – In adherence to research ethics, the “City” hereinafter refers to one of the cities in Metro Manila that serves as the subject of this study.

City Ordinance – This refers to the public policy, which serves as another subject of this study, that was enacted in the City to regulate Internet café operations.

Implementation – This refers to the execution of the law in which various stakeholders, organizations, procedures, and techniques work together to put policies into effect with a view of attaining policy goals (Stewart et al., 2008).

Self-Administered Survey - This is a data collection technique in which the respondent reads the survey questions and records his or her answers without the presence of a trained interviewer.

Conceptual Framework

(The independent variable in the study is the City Ordinance, while the dependent variables are policy communication/dissemination and compliance/desired behavior. The mediating variable is policy implementation, which is affected by some factors, i.e., political will, funding support, and leadership skill. These are just a few of the contributing factors to poor implementation. How the policy is communicated to the

citizens, i.e., whether monologic or dialogic, is associated with how the policy is implemented. If political will, sufficient funding support, proper direction, etc., are present during implementation, political leaders would likely engage in participatory or dialogic communication. Otherwise, they would only practice one-way or monologic communication, which is associated with poor implementation. On the other hand, policy compliance or behavior change is associated with how the policy is communicated/disseminated and whether it is participatory or one-way.

Theoretical Framework

The Integrated Model of Communication for Social Change detailed how social change can occur through a process of community discourse that leads to collective action that affects the welfare of communities as a whole as well as the individual members of those communities, according to Reardon, (2003). The model depicted a dynamic, iterative process that begins with an external or internal catalyst/stimulus to the community. This catalyst then initiates community discourse, which, when effective, can result in collaborative action and the settlement of a common problem..

According to Freire, 1993; Walton, (1998), dialogue can be defined as a courteous attitude toward people and a method of developing awareness about social realities (including power inequality and economic relations). A dialogical technique to enhancing awareness through interpersonal contact is the inverse of one-way education, in which an expert communicates information to an empty/ignorant receiver/audience. Hence, dialogue communication seeks to establish a relationship that encourages contemplation and probable action.

According to Agunga (1997), communication is not merely the transmission of information but entails creation and stimulation of comprehension of the subject or matter being conveyed. It is the expression of people's social relationships. People

should not be coerced into adopting new behaviors, regardless of how advantageous they appear to agencies and public. The people should be encouraged to engage instead of simply adopting new behaviors merely based on the communicated knowledge. This notion of communication was the central thought of the theories articulated by Brazilian educator Paulo Freire (1970), whose writings and experiences influenced the participatory communication movement. In the 1960s and early 1970s, Freire's work in northeastern Brazil challenged mainstream notions of development communication, particularly when applied to literacy teaching. In his study, he claimed that development initiatives had failed to teach small farmers because they were more focused on convincing the subjects of the benefits of adopting the introduced innovations. According to Freire, development initiatives attempted to domesticate foreign notions, provide information, and force local populations to accept Western ideas and behaviors without considering how such practices may fit in with existing cultures. The premise of such programs was an authoritarian ideology that contradicted the principle or core of communication which was community involvement and education. With the suggestion of Freire on the notion of liberal education which defined communication as discussion and participation, the objective of communication should be conscientization, which Freire characterized as free discussion that stressed cultural identification, trust, and commitment. His perspective was dubbed "dialogical pedagogy," and it emphasized equity in distribution and active grassroots participation as essential concepts. According to Freire, communication should give a sense of ownership to the people involved in a particular program by making them share their related experiences freely and comfortably. On the other hand, education is not the transfer of

knowledge or communication of information to those who need it, but it is an artistic way of exploring the world.

Information is very important in any policy process but its effectiveness to change behavior is contingent on how it is effectively communicated. Duram and Brown (1999) found that two-way communication methods were more effective than one-way communication methods.

Finally, implementation is also a very important stage in policymaking as successful policy outcomes depend not only on designing effective systems but also on managing their implementation (Brinkerhoff & Crosby 2002).

Chapter II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The goal of the present study is to understand how a City Ordinance is communicated and disseminated to the people, thus the purpose of this chapter is to review not only public policy and its communication but also other related literature and contributing factors, policy implementation and the factors that affect it, and the role of communication in the efficacy of public policy, policy compliance, and behavior change. Through this, further insight on how political leaders formulate and implement public policies or any policy programs may be gained for the development of the study.

Government Communication as a Policy Instrument

“Communication can help to discover and understand problems, as well as potential solutions, among those engaged in the collective effort as well as those targeted ... In addition to educating and mobilizing, communication sites serve as venues through which groups can contest interpretations of these problems and projects, which are ... complex.” – Karin Wilkins (1998)

In a book titled, “Carrots, Sticks & Sermons: Policy Instruments and Their Evaluation”, carrots, sticks, and sermons referred to the economy, regulation, and information respectively. According to Vedung and van der Doelen (1998), the communications of government were usually regarded as the “sermons,” which Vedung defined as:

“Efforts to use government knowledge and data to influence consumer and producer behavior in a direction consistent with government goals and desires” and/or “gather information to further their goals and ambitions.” (Vedung and van der Doelen, 1998).

Vedung's concept defined two main dimensions of information tool use and the general purpose to which they might be applied, namely influencing consumer and producer behavior in economic transactions and managing or collecting information for politico-administrative purposes. According to the researchers (Saward, 1992; Edelman, 1988; Hornik, 1988; Jahn et al., 2005; Howlett, 2000), the main distinction between the two is whether communication activities were intended to serve as devices primarily aimed at manipulating policy actors and processes or the social and economic factors involved in the production of goods and services.

Substantive government communication policy instruments are approaches or mechanisms that rely on the use of information to influence the behavior of individuals directly or indirectly involved in the production, consumption, and distribution of many types of products and services in society. Procedural tools, on the other hand, have an indirect impact on production, consumption, and distribution processes rather than directly influencing the behavior of people involved in policymaking. However, there is another component to consider: the stage of the production process or policy cycle on which various communication instruments are focused according to Howlett (2009). According to the researchers (Mikenberg, 2001; Sulitzeanu-Kenan, 2007; Salmon, 1989), many studies on the use of procedural information tools, for example, focused on the role of government communications as part of the government's agenda-setting process or its function in policy implementation.

According to Howlett (2009), the government information campaign is the most visible and widely seen type of tool which is the substantive, back-end tool focused on efforts to change consumers' behavior. According to this researcher, however, front-end communication initiatives targeted at changing producer behavior

by providing customers with product and process knowledge (product information) were also prevalent.

Communication tools are classified into four broad categories. Substantive Producer-Directed Tools: Notification Instruments and Moral Suasion is the first. According to Adler and Pittle (1984), this tool is a notification device that conveys true information to the intelligent target. The belief implicit in the notification technique was that the target, if informed of the facts, would make the appropriate decision.

According to Jahn et al. (2005), notification tools are typically enacted in regulations and are intended to provide consumers with information, giving them an opportunity to form better decisions or overcome information asymmetries between producers and consumers, with the expectation that they will change their behaviors in accordance with the government's goals. Similarly, Moral suasion, according to Stanbury and Fulton (1984), is a more direct call from governments to producers in which voluntary behavior is advocated with the prospect of coercion if refused. Many countries, according to Bardach (1989), have administered important aspects of their financial systems in this manner, such as asking banks, taxpayers, and other financial institutions to act in a certain way (e.g., keep interest rates low or allow certain groups to borrow funds) with the implicit or explicit threat of direct government regulation if requests were ignored or unfulfilled.

Substantive Consumer-Directed Tools: Exhortation and Persuasion Instruments is another category. According to Adler & Pittle (1984), this technique is aimed at customers and is classified as "persuasion instruments," which are persuasion schemes that communicate messages that may or may not contain

factual information and actively seek to influence target audiences to change their behavior. The most common form of government communication was an appeal from political leaders to diverse social actors, pushing people to follow a government's lead in certain sectors of social or economic life according to Cobb & Elder (1975). Exhortation, according to Stanbury and Fulton (1984), is pure political leadership that calls for calm, improved behavior, and high principles.

Another category of government communication tools described by Stanbury and Fulton (1984) as monitoring and information disclosure instruments, i.e., freedom of information and privacy laws, were procedural tools that affect agenda-setting and policy formulation.

Therefore, the different classifications of government communications can help officials decide on the appropriate communication tool to address different social issues confronting our society today. However, the traditional way of communicating the citizens may not be as effective as the new means of communication with the advent of the information age.

Public Policy Delivery System in Infobesity Age

Influencing the behavior of the target audience is a difficult endeavor especially in this day of age where people, irrespective of age and status in life, are predisposed to use new communication technology. The government may consider shifting from traditional to new ways of communication that shape the world today.

The advent of new technology has created a mismatch between how the government communicates with citizens and how citizens interact and digest information. The fundamental idea driving the mismatch is that the environment for

information and communication is changing as people adopt new modes of communication, while the government remains relatively unchanged in its mode of communication. It must be indispensable for the government sector to adapt to the rapidly changing information environment typified by information overload and the advent of visual communication platforms such as YouTube. According to Ahn (2012), the traditional government communication, such as official documents and public announcements, is increasingly ineffective when compared to the vivid imagery and emotionally charged appeal of visual communication, which is starting to dominate the information environment and influence the general public. People today choose concise information over long, comprehensive, and verbose information due to information overload. Furthermore, visual communication tends to condense and compress information when compared to what is often conveyed in writing according to McLuhan & Gordon (2003). As a result, the move to visual communication speeds up information processing.

The information or message must be provided in an understandable manner. YouTube, for example, uses visuals (video) as a medium of communication. Users would broadcast and view video snippets instead of writing and reading. Visual communication has the ability to emotionally appeal to the audience because it creates a direct connection between the audience and the content offered through visuals that are utilized to convey the message. It possesses a comparative advantage in reaching the target audience instead of text communication as communication using pictures and visuals are thought to be more interesting and easy to understand. According to Tybout & Artz (1994), the vividness of the communication increases attention of the audience, making the information more accessible.

Ultimately, public policy must be communicated to citizens in a comprehensible manner, and this can be addressed through new technologies. However, the success of public policy communication is determined by how well it adapts to our changing information environment and people' information-receiving behavior, as communication flaws may raise the risk of policy failure.

What is Public Policy?

As mentioned in the previous chapter, public policy has been defined by many scholars in different ways but were all headed toward the same goal—societal betterment. The government usually formulated Public policy as its response to societal problems and an initiative to enhance people's lives or the government's system. Governments typically employ traditional policy tools such as legislation, fines, regulations, taxes, and subsidies, and other laws, in their efforts to influence or modify the citizens' behaviors for the common good. There are underlying reasons for the wide range of government policies but mostly, they are intended to provide economic, social, and community advantages. Examples of these are regulations that discourage business collusion, which can lead to lower costs and more consumer choice, as well as regulations that modify the citizens' undesirable behaviors that could adversely affect the whole community if ignored.

According to some scholars, traditional strategies for influencing behavior are effective in many areas of public policy. However, there are social problems where Influencing human behavior is tough and complex, and the success of traditional policy measures may be restricted in the absence of additional instruments and an understanding of how to engage citizens in cooperative behavioral change. This could lead to so-called wicked problems in public policy.

Thus, it is important to understand why many policies and initiatives provoke controversy, fail to fulfill stated goals, have unanticipated consequences, or are impossible to coordinate and monitor. This may be addressed by a discourse on the complexity of policy implementation and the elements that influence it.

Public Policy Implementation

Implementation is the process through which diverse individuals and organizations collaborate with the use of procedures and strategies to put policies into action in order to achieve goals, according to Stewart, Hedge, & Lester (2008). According to Pressman & Wildavsky (1973), it is a process, an output, and an outcome that involves actors, organizations, and control mechanisms, as well as a relationship between goal-setting and goal-attainment actions.

Public policy must be executed correctly in order to benefit citizens (Stewart, Hedge, & Lester, 2008), and its success is correlated positively with how it is implemented. However, one concern with policy implementation is a lack of sufficient direction or recommendations on how to apply it. According to Michie et al. (2008), "theory provides a useful foundation for designing interventions to change behavior but offers little guidance on how to do so."

Factors Affecting the Implementation of Public Policy

Meter and Horn (1975) noted that numerous environmental elements, such as the current economic, social, and political conditions, can influence the implementation process.

Other scholars have discussed the challenges of policy implementation. Many policies are not adopted or performed as intended, or a policy intervention may

simply be poorly managed or compromised by political meddling. Sometimes manpower is unavailable or facilities are insufficient, and frontline implementers are unable to carry out an intervention due to a lack of motivation or skill. Policy design may also be inadequately structured, or the initial concept may not have been well communicated to workers. Furthermore, policy participants may not be recognized precisely, insufficient in numbers, or are uncooperative according to Rossi, Lipsey, & Freeman (2004). Some scholars (Meter & Horn, 1975; Mazmanian & Sabatier, 1989; Brinkerhoff & Crosby, 2002; Lipsky, 2010; Bardach, 1977; Goggin, Bowman, Lester & O'Toole, 1990; Fox, Bayat & Ferriera, 2006; Wali, 2010; Stoker, 1991; Vedung, 2017) conclude that a policy cannot be effectively implemented because of lack of resources i.e. professional, technical, and financial resources, incentives, competent staff; negative attitude among implementers; lack of communication between organizations; lack of formal commitment to statutory goals; no adequate autonomy, authority delegation and adaptability; inter-organizational complexity and conflict; influence of economic, political, and social factors; a lack of precise technical expertise or administrative competencies in the overwhelming self-serving motives of street-level bureaucrats; lack of organizational desire; increased demand for services; imprecise, confusing, or conflicting goal expectations; challenges in reaching goals, and involuntary clients.

The constraints mentioned above are just among the identified various elements influencing policy implementation. However, policy communication should be given utmost attention especially if the objective requires behavior change and people's commitment to a sustained desired behavior.

People are more inclined to commit when it is convenient for them to do so. Furthermore, people will unlikely commit to things that are inconsistent with their views or behavior. Thus, communication campaigns aiming at influencing the attitude or behavior may be necessary in order to convince the society to behave in a way as desired by the government.

Information Dissemination

Governments use information to affect behavior based on the rational choice model's underlying assumption that if individuals are aware that their actions and/or activities have negative effects, they would avoid or eliminate them. It is obvious that in some circumstances, information efforts alone are insufficient to affect the behavior of huge numbers of individuals over time. According to Kathryn Mearns (2016), information and exhortation were among the least successful strategies for changing behavior (Campbell, 1963; Bandura, 1980). Similarly, these scholars noted that empirical evidence failed to support the assumption of persuasion theory that exposure to information results in a shift in attitude, which leads to a shift in conduct.

While the insights from prior research are true, communication undoubtedly remains to be a vital component of any successful policy or program but is contingent on how it is enacted. Sufficient information, including technical knowledge of the matter, must be communicated strategically to those involved.

Numerous research pointed out the importance of communication in a decision-making process. A comparative case study on the participatory decision-making process discovered that the quality and availability of information used in deliberation had a number of significant consequences. Information was positively

related to the level of acceptance attained, which was critical to making competent decisions and mediated the building of social competence, according to the researchers (Cole et al., 1996; Carnes et al., 1998; Leach, Pelkey, & Sabatier, 2002; Bradbury, Branch, & Malone, 2003; Leach & Sabatier, 2003). Bradbury, Branch, and Malone (2003) discovered that information disclosure was critical for framing, selecting, and prioritizing issues. Likewise, Beierle and Cayford (2002) observed significant positive connections between a lead agency's responsiveness (i.e., commitment to and contact with participants) and the aggregate measure of success. Also, according to Aronoff and Gunter (1994), ambiguous communications are a feature of agency-community relations that can have a negative impact on the quality of outcomes.

Communication, as an exchange of knowledge, information, ideas, attitude, and feelings among people through channels and symbols (Hasan, 2013), is important in all stages of policy-making, especially in the implementation stage. According to Ahn (2012), the effective communication of government to the society is a significant aspect in the success of policy implementation. A policy's success is frequently defined by outcome- and process-related criteria. Substantive policy outcomes (e.g., the issue was solved)

- Outcomes related to social capacity (e.g., stakeholders trust each other more)
- Degree of acceptance or satisfaction with the process and outcomes

Process-related criteria can be separated into two categories: fairness and competence, according to the researchers (Petts & Leach, 2000; Renn, Webler, & Wiedemann, 1995; Tuler 2011). According to Eiger & McAvoy (1992), both are concerned with participant interactions. Fairness is concerned with providing suitable

chances for involvement, whereas competence is concerned with communicating effectively, sharing knowledge appropriately, and making the best-informed decisions possible.

Theories of Behavior Change

“Policy development in the context of behavioral change is notoriously difficult.”

(Jackson, 2005, p. 3)

“The sheer complexity of human behaviors and motivations makes it very hard to predict with certainty what the impacts of policy interventions on people’s behavior are going to be.”

(Jackson, 2005, p.

119)

While public policies are designed to be interventions to influence behavior, the following is a review of some theories on behavior change that could provide better insight on the reasons why public policies or programs fail to influence behavior.

There are a few key points to remember from a wide range of theories when building tools or policy initiatives to impact behavior. According to Kathryn Mearns (2016), the behavior is particularly resistant to change due to the following:

- People are creatures of habit, and we strive for maximum gain with the least amount of work.
- Even if people are informed about health dangers (e.g., smoking, obesity), information and exhortation are among the least successful strategies of altering behavior, according to the researchers (Bandura, 1980; Campbell, 1963).

- People are focused on the short term rather than the long term (our predecessors' immediate survival was crucial, but the highly gradual and sluggish speed of environmental change represents a cognitive obstacle, according to Kollmuss & Agyeman (2002).
- People do not always respond well when they are instructed what to do, according to Branson et al. (2012).

However, early persuasion theory argued that successful persuasion was based on three crucial factors: how trustworthy or credible the speaker or source is; how persuasive the message or arguments are; and how responsive the audience or recipient is (Hovland et. al., 1953).

According to persuasion theory, exposure to knowledge leads to a change in attitude, which leads to a change in conduct. The information-deficit model's basic hypothesis was that people do not have enough or right information. Hence, people will be more inclined to change their behaviors if they were provided with more information. This somehow relates to the belief implicit in the notification approach of communication, as discussed previously, that the target audience will make the appropriate decision once apprised of the facts. Although this appears to be a logical hypothesis, empirical evidence does not support it, and substantial shortcomings of this linear model have been identified, according to the researchers (McKenzie-Mohr, 2002; Petty et al., 2002). Despite the theory's shortcomings, the importance of the fundamental parts may still be seen in behavior. In a land manager behavior, for example, it has been demonstrated that the source of advice of farmers (the farm advisor and the organization to which they belong) and the persuasiveness

of their arguments were equally relevant as other factors, as noted by the researchers (Juntti & Potter, 2002; Vanclay, 2004, Silgo & Massey, 2007).

One of the most popular persuasion models, the Elaboration Likelihood Model (Petty & Cacioppo, 1981, 1986), proposed that there are two types of psychological processes involved in attitude modification – the central and peripheral processing channels. The periphery method will be used if the target audience's motivation or ability to engage with the message is low. This could result in either a direct behavior change or an attitude adjustment followed by a behavior change. When a person is extremely driven and pays close attention, the message will go through the central processing channel. This method is more likely to result in long-term attitude modification. This idea provides some recommendations for effective persuasion:

- It is critical to utilize personally engaging messages since they are more likely to lead to the use of the central processing route through an emotional and imaginative appeal.
- The message should be immediate and direct.
- Use a single, well-placed, really uplifting message.
- Persuasive appeals must rely on reputable sources.
- Use commitments to demonstrate involvement.
- Identify retrieval cues, or factors that will assist individuals recall and remember the persuasive message (Jackson, 2005, p. 109).

According to the linked scientific data base in Social Learning Theory, social learning is a potent avenue of behavioral change (Jackson, 2005, p. 112). This

approach emphasizes the crucial role of government being the lead in the society's behavioral change. This means that failure by government leaders to model the behavioral changes that the policy seeks to achieve would severely damage any information and persuasion initiatives. Moreover, Bandura's (1980) Social Learning Theory emphasizes the following:

- Receiving a reward or a penalty will influence how a person chooses to behave in the future. Rewards can be monetary or nonmonetary, and they might take the shape of material things or satisfaction of humanitarian desires.
- People learn through seeing the actions or behaviors of others such as parents, peers, and those that can be seen in the media especially those they depicted as role model who have a strong influence on their own behavior.

Chapter III

METHODOLOGY

The aforementioned prohibitions in City Ordinance were used as parameters in determining the level of implementation of the City Ordinance and level of awareness by Internet café operators.

The following research questions influenced the methodology of this study:

1. To what extent was the City Ordinance implemented by the Internet café operators inside their Internet cafés?
2. How knowledgeable are Internet café operators in the City about the City Ordinance?
3. How did Internet café users behave inside the Internet cafés vis-à-vis the objectives of the City Ordinance?
4. What were the experiences/problems encountered by the parents of children frequenting Internet cafés?
5. What were the strategies used by barangay officials, if any, in the dissemination of the City Ordinance, and how was the City Ordinance communicated to the Internet café operators?

Research Design

This study focuses on uncovering and describing how the City Ordinance was communicated/disseminated to the Internet café operators in the City. The strategy used in communicating the City Ordinance will be determined through interviews with

the concerned officials. The Internet café users' and Internet café operators' level of awareness shall also be identified, and the results shall be associated with how the City Ordinance was communicated/disseminated to the Internet café operators. Thus, the research design suitable for this study is quantitative, specifically descriptive research design.

Descriptive research design is a scientific method that involves monitoring and describing a subject's activity without interfering with it in any manner. This signifies that the subject is being observed in its entirely natural and unaltered natural environment. According to Grove, Burns, and Gray (2012), Descriptive Designs can be used to create theory, identify problems and justifications with present practice, make judgments, or find out the actions of others who are in the same situations. Moreover, When there is limited knowledge about a certain occurrence, descriptive studies are used. The researcher just observes, describes, and documents numerous elements of a phenomenon. Quantitative research designs are broadly classed as either nonexperimental or experimental. Descriptive designs are nonexperimental and are used to characterize, distinguish, or investigate associations, rather than direct correlations, between or among variables, groups, or circumstances.

The three types of research methods used in descriptive research design are observational, survey, and case study, according to (Jackson, 2009). The observational method is also known as field observation, and it involves closely observing animal and human behavior. In a survey, participants respond to questions posed by interviews or questionnaires. Finally, an in-depth examination shall be done to the individual or a group in a case study. As this study uses a

descriptive research design, it shall utilize the observational and survey research methods.

Sampling Procedure

This study used a mixed sample strategy, which includes criterion sampling, random sampling, and snowball sampling, as detailed below. To be more specific, Random sampling schemes are classified as quantitative, whilst nonrandom sampling schemes are classified as qualitative. This is a false dichotomy, as Onwuegbuzie and Leech (2005a) point out. Rather, in quantitative and qualitative investigations, both random and non-random sampling strategies can be used. The suitability of each strategy is determined by the study goal, objective, purpose, and questions, according to Onwuegbuzie and Collins (2007).

According to Patton (2002, in some circumstances, it is beneficial to choose sampling procedures which we can identify a group of individuals with different experiences. Purposeful sampling is a technique for identifying and selecting examples to make the most use of limited resources, and consider the persons, groups, and environments if they are "information-rich" , according to Patton, (2002). According to Creswell & Plano Clark (2011), in this sampling procedure, the researcher shall identify and select individuals or groups who have knowledge and experience relating to the subject of interest or under study. Bernard (2002) and Spradley (1979) emphasized that in addition to knowledge and experience, it is important that the subject of interest is available and willing to participate, and has the ability to communicate/articulate/express experiences and views.

First, criterion sampling was applied in this study for the selection of the second district of the City as the population of interest since Internet cafés are concentrated in this district. Second, random sampling was used for the selection of Internet cafés and Internet café users for an equal chance of inclusion in the sample. Third, snowball sampling was employed for the selection of households to establish Internet café-related problems involving the youth within the households as there have been no such cases recorded in the City.

Criterion Sampling for Selection of Barangays

This study used criteria sampling and sampled the barangays in the City that the researcher can most get the needed information. Criterion sampling entails the review and study of cases that meet some predetermined criterion of importance, according to Patton (2002).

As the target respondents for this study are the Internet cafés and its customers, the criterion observed in this study is the concentration of Internet Cafés in the City. The City has two districts, and Internet cafés are highly concentrated in District 2, while only a few can be found in District 1 based on the list obtained from the City Hall. Thus, District 2 became the population of interest for this study. An underlying factor for this could be that the City's central business district is located in District 2.

According to some scholars (Alli et al., 1991; Chan et al., 1995; Ghosh et al., 1995), the location of a business has an impact on its success. Nurul Indarti (2004), on the other hand, categorized Internet Cafés as a service business because they provide services to their customers. This is comparable to the retail industry, as defined by Levy and Weitz (1998, p. 7), which sells items and services directly to

consumers. Hanink (1997) noted that the business location with high market density is the optimal location for service enterprises (i.e., retail businesses) or other consumer service providers. The traffic and population densities also contribute to the success in this line of business. It is also advantageous for businesses to be situated in a retail cluster or in the heart of commercial activities, which mostly happens in a central business district. According to Mazze (1972), a retail grouping is a group of retailers with the same target market. Nelson's (1958) theory of cumulative attraction suggested that shops do profit from agglomeration. This suggests that a cluster of identical and complementary retailing activities will have more attracting power than standalone stores engaging in the same retailing activities, according to Levy and Weitz (1998). Shoe stores, clothes stores, cosmetics stores, and perfume shops, for example, appear to fare better when they are close to one another. Similarly, stationery stores, photocopying centers, computer rentals, and Internet cafés appear to benefit more when grouped together in one location.

Another criterion considered for the sampling is the legitimacy of computer shop/Internet café establishments, which essentially means that the computer shops should be duly registered under the Business Permit and Licensing Office of City (BPLO) under Section 5 of the City Ordinance.

According to Baldwin, Cave, & Lodge (2011), there are three ways to look at regulation enumerated as follows: "a specific set of directives in which regulation is the establishment of a binding set of rules to be followed by a body dedicated to a specific purpose; as deliberate state influence, where regulation has a broader meaning and encompasses any official acts intended to influence economic or social conduct; as all types of social control or influence in which all behavioral systems are

regulatory". In layman's terms, the local government of the City cannot regulate business establishments that are unknown to them unless they go beyond the list of registered Internet cafés. Thus, legitimacy was considered as another criterion for sampling.

Random Sampling for the Internet Cafés in District 2

All 13 barangays in the second district of the City were included in the study. 50% of the Internet cafés in each barangay were randomly selected. The registered names of the Internet cafés per barangay were placed inside a fishbowl then picked randomly. This process was done for all the barangays. After the sampling of Internet cafés was done, sampling for Internet café users followed.

Random Sampling for Internet Café Users

It has been observed that the personal computers (PCs) inside Internet cafés were numbered. The respondents, which belong among the customers of each Internet café, were randomly chosen based on the numbers indicated on the PCs they used. Random sampling was used to give all the customers equal chances to answer the questions in the survey and prevent bias. Each PC number was written on tiny pieces of paper that were then placed in a fishbowl. To get enough sample, 50% of the PC numbers were picked from a fishbowl, and the corresponding users of the PCs were then chosen as the survey respondents. Furthermore, it was already considered beforehand that in cases where a PC with no user was picked for the survey, another number shall be picked to complete the target sample composed of 50% of the customers. A total of 93 Internet cafés have been selected in 13 barangays, i.e., 4 from Barangay I, 6 from Barangay II, 8 from Barangay III, 6 from Barangay IV, 7 from Barangay V, 4 from Barangay VI, 4 from Barangay VII, 9 from

Barangay VIII, 5 from Barangay IX, 13 from Barangay X, 7 from Barangay XI, 8 from Barangay XII, and 12 from Barangay XIII.

From 93 Internet cafés, there were a total of 772 Internet users / respondents, which comprised the following: Barangay I – 29, Barangay II – 46, Barangay III – 52, Barangay IV – 35, Barangay V – 53, Barangay VI – 37, Barangay VII – 25, Barangay VIII – 67, Barangay IX – 36, Barangay X – 106, Barangay XI – 74, Barangay XII – 89, and Barangay XIII – 123.

Snowball Sampling for Parents

The parents' dilemma about the negative effects of Internet cafés / computer shops on their children seemed to have become an ordinary issue in society today. Cases of students skipping classes have been noted, and worse, others have quit their studies because of their frequent visits and longer hours of stay in computer shops. The City is not isolated from this case. Thus, for this study and to establish whether Internet café-related problems involving the youth and especially students exist in the City, a survey was conducted to explore the experiences and problems encountered by the parents of children who frequent Internet cafés. The participants for this survey included the parents (mother or father) of 50 chosen households in the second district of the City where Internet cafés were concentrated, specifically those who have encountered problems with their children who frequent Internet cafés. The researchers believed that the sample was sufficient enough to represent District 2 given the objective of the survey, which is to establish whether Internet café-related problems among the youth and students, in particular, exist in the City. Furthermore, some scholars said that If the goal was to gain insights into a phenomenon, individuals, or events rather than generalize a population, the

researcher should actively choose persons, groups, and settings that will maximize comprehension of the observed phenomenon. Particularly, representation can be improved by ensuring that sampling decisions are informed by the research goal (e.g., prediction, complex phenomenon comprehension), research objective (e.g., exploration, prediction), research purpose (e.g., triangulation, complementarity), and research question(s). The sample size should also be primarily defined by the research objectives, questions, and, finally, the research design. Small samples may be used in exploratory or basic quantitative research, according to Onwuegbuzie & Collins (2007). According to Holloway and Wheeler (2002), the sample size has no bearing on the significance or quality of the study.

While a sample of 50 participants/households is small vis-à-vis the total population of the City, it cannot be underestimated as the study explores one of the problems influenced by the society's culture and structures that can weaken society's stability if ignored. This case could also be viewed as individual problems within the family. However, individual difficulties are frequently based in problems arising from features of society itself, according to sociology (Mills, 1959). The family has been defined as the basic unit of society. It is undeniable that there are people who do not give much attention to the problems that occur within the family, but based on the functionalist theory, (Google book: Social Problems by Alex Thio, Jim Taylor):

“Every aspect of society — the home, the school, the economy, the government, and other social organizations and groupings — serves a purpose for the greater good. The family nurtures children, the school educates them, the economy provides jobs, and the government provides

security, among other things. To achieve a stable social order, all aspects of society rely on one another. Thus, the family relies on the school to teach its children, the school relies on the family to provide emotional support, and both the school and the family rely on the government to create a safe environment. We have a situation of dysfunction when some parts of society fail to perform their functions, causing the network of interdependence among all parts to be disrupted. As a result of the dysfunction, social problems such as high rates of delinquency, crime, unemployment, and poverty will emerge.”

The premise behind this is that the family plays a vital role in society. It is the researcher's view that the family, as the fundamental unit of society, should be strengthened and integrated into the development process. It is entitled to extensive protection and assistance. Fifty participants may be a small portion compared to the total population of the City, but the results could promote awareness and encourage realization to political leaders and other segments of the society that Internet café-related problems are present and should be given much attention.

Negative conditions and behaviors, according to some sociologists, are not deemed societal problems unless they are acknowledged as such by policymakers, large numbers of lay individuals, or other elements of our society. A social problem arises when a social entity (such as a social change organization, the news media, or important politicians) begins to draw attention to a state or behavior that is seen undesirable and in need of correction. Thus, the sampling of 50 parents should reach the attention of policymakers and other segments of the society, particularly in

the City, for Internet café-related problems to be recognized as negative conditions and behaviors that would adversely affect the society if ignored.

Since there has been no recorded knowledge of Internet café-related problems involving youth in the City, snowball sampling was deemed appropriate in selecting 50 participants for this survey. Snowball sampling which also known as chain-referral sampling, is a nonprobability or nonrandom sampling approach used when the attributes to be possessed by samples are not common and hard to obtain. Primary data sources nominate another prospective primary data source to be used in the research using this sampling strategy. Moreover, snowball sampling employs recommendations from original individuals to produce additional subjects. Thus, members of the sample group were recruited through a network of referrals. when this method was applied in the study.

Snowball sampling has three patterns described as follows: linear snowball sampling, in which a sample group is formed from only one subject, and the subject, and the subject as well as the recruited referral both provide only one new referral, exponential non-discriminative snowball sampling, in which the first subject recruited to the sample group provides multiple referrals, and each new referral is investigated until primary data from a sufficient number of samples is collected, and exponential discriminative snowball sampling, in which subjects provide multiple referrals, but only one new subject is recruited among them.

During the survey, the goal of this study was for each of the 13 barangays to be represented with at least two samples. Hence, the researcher applied the linear and exponential discriminative snowball sampling to the study. Contact for each barangay was then established through relatives, friends, and friends of friends to

identify one or two initial cases. All contacts were asked if they knew households in their barangays facing Internet café-related problems involving the younger members of the family. Then, the survey was conducted with the identified subjects and referrals. During the survey proper, there was an instance where the first subject in one barangay provided multiple referrals. Exponential discriminative snowball sampling was then applied, which means only one referral was considered, as the goal of the survey was for all barangays in District 2 to be represented. Snowball sampling continued until a total of 50 participants were formed.

Data Collection

This study utilized parallel data gathering, i.e., a self-administered survey was done on the Internet café users while observing their behavior. Similarly, open-ended survey questionnaires were administered to the Internet café operators while observing their establishments. Concurrent mixed-method data collecting procedures have been used to validate one type of data against another, alter data for comparison, or answer different sorts of queries, according to Creswell & Plano Clark, (2007). In many situations, the same individuals provided both qualitative and quantitative data, making data comparison easier.

The interviews, observations, and questionnaires were the tools used for the data collection for this study. All of these methods were done in the afternoon, i.e. from 2:00 to 7:00 PM. This was the chosen schedule to conduct the research as the influx of Internet café users was high during this period.

Observation Method

Observation is one of the most significant strategies for collecting thorough data in qualitative research, especially when a combination of oral and visual data is required, according to Anum (2017). Marshall and Rossman (1989) defined observation as the methodical description of events, actions, and artifacts in the social milieu chosen for research. Observations allowed the researcher to characterize existing situations using the five senses.

Participant Observation

Participant observation, according to DeMunck and Sobo (1998), is the major approach employed by anthropologists conducting fieldwork. Fieldwork entails active looking, memory improvement, informal interviewing, comprehensive field notes, and, maybe most significantly, patience, according to DeWalt & DeWalt (2002). Moreover, participant observation allows researchers to learn about the behaviors of the people being studied in their natural environment by witnessing and engaging in those activities. Participant observation, as described by Schensul, Schensul, and LeCompte (1999), is the process of learning by being exposed to or involved in the daily or routinary activities of participants in researcher's setting. Bernard (1994) contributed to this knowledge by stating that participant observation necessitates some deceit and impression manipulation. Meanwhile, according to DeWalt and DeWalt (2002), According to DeWalt and DeWalt (2002), this form of observation should be utilized to strengthen the validity of the study because observations can assist the researcher obtain a better grasp of the context and phenomenon under study.

Nonparticipant Observation

Nonparticipant observation is described as a research approach in which the researcher observes the subjects of his or her study with knowledge but without actively participating in the circumstance under investigation (“non-participant observation.” A Dictionary of Sociology. Encyclopedia.com.).

This study employed both participant observation and nonparticipant observation. There were two observation sheets developed for the observation—a checklist on the implementation of the City Ordinance by Internet café operators that contained items requiring a purely nonparticipant method, and another checklist for the Internet café operators’ awareness of the City Ordinance, containing items that require a combination of nonparticipant and participant methods, as well as one informal interview question given to the Internet café owner or the person-in-charge when the survey was conducted.

Applying participant observation in this study, the researcher pretended as a customer and rented a computer for one hour. While inside the Internet café, the researcher put a checkmark under items in the checklists that corresponded to the observations. After the observation sheets, both for the participant and nonparticipant methods were filled out, the researcher engaged in an informal chat with the Internet café owners or persons-in-charge, and then asked one question that was included in the observation sheet.

Survey Questionnaires

After the observation was done, the interview with the Internet café operators or persons-in-charge and the administration of questionnaires to the Internet café users followed. Two questionnaires were developed for the survey conducted inside

the Internet cafés. A semi-structured questionnaire (Appendix 1) for the interview with Internet café operators was developed to assess their awareness of the City Ordinance. The questionnaire not only contained closed questions answerable by yes or no but also open-ended follow-up questions so that the respondents can give their insights freely and elaborate further on the matter being asked. During the interview, the researcher took notes and observed while the Internet café operator being interviewed discussed his answers. Open-ended questions can provide richness to survey results that is difficult, if not impossible, to create with closed questions; hence, incorporating some on their own or as follow-ups to closed items may offer considerable benefits, according to Schuman (1972). Moreover, a structured questionnaire (Appendix 2) was also developed and administered to Internet café users after the interview with the operators. The results of this questionnaire can help determine the level of implementation of the City Ordinance by the Internet café operators. This can also corroborate with the answers from the questionnaire administered to the parents as discussed below. The researcher intended to develop a structured questionnaire for Internet café users, which was answerable only by yes or no, considering that they may have a short attention span for the survey. Internet café users who were at the elementary level were assisted in answering the questionnaire.

To get the cooperation of both the Internet operators and users, the researcher did her best to explain how to answer the questionnaire properly and asked for their cooperation humbly especially from the Internet café operators. The purpose of the survey was also explained as well as its significance for the completion of the researcher's master's degree. The researcher also offered to

shoulder the costs of the two-hour computer rental used by the Internet café users in the duration of the survey as a way to convince them to cooperate for the interview.

Furthermore, another semi-structured questionnaire, as shown below (Appendix 3), was also developed and administered to the parents of children frequenting the Internet cafés. This questionnaire was developed to explore the experiences/problems encountered by the parents to establish whether Internet café-related problems among the youth and students, in particular, were present in the City. Although the questionnaire provided choices, it also included enough space wherein respondents can freely discuss further their experiences/problems encountered.

Chapter IV

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1: Profile of respondents (Internet café users)

From 13 barangays, a total of 93 Internet cafés is covered in this study, i.e., 4 from Barangay I, 6 from Barangay II, 8 from Barangay III, 6 from Barangay IV, 7 from Barangay V, 4 from Barangay VI, 4 from Barangay VII, 9 from Barangay VIII, 5 from Barangay IX, 13 from Barangay X, 7 from Barangay XI, 8 from Barangay XII, and 12 from Barangay XIII. From 93 Internet cafés, a total of 772 internet users became the respondents that consist of 17 females (2.2%) and 755 males (97.8%). Based on Figure 1, most Internet users in the observed Internet cafés are males, thus coinciding with different studies conducted on Internet usage. In addition, as a result of a study of gender and Internet in terms of frequency, researchers indicate that men use the Internet more frequently and for longer periods of time than women (Winker, 2005), confirming the findings of previous studies in other countries that male users predominate in Internet cafés. Meanwhile, Furuholt, Kristiansen, and Wahid (2008) studied Indonesian and Tanzanian Internet usage at cyber cafés and discovered that cyber cafés are quite popular in these countries, with males being

the dominant users at the cafés. Moreover, in a survey of Internet café users in Lahore, Pakistan, the majority (91.7%) of café users were male. In addition, Li and Kirkup (2007) studied Internet usage among Chinese and British students and discovered that men in both nations played more computer games than women.

Table 1. Age summary of 772 Internet café users

Variable	No. of observations	Mean	Standard deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Age	772	12.08	3.79	7	35

Table 1 shows a summary of the ages of 772 respondents. The youngest respondent is 7 years old, while the oldest is 35 years old. The average age of these respondents is 12.08 years old, which deviates from the average by 3.79 years.

Figure 2

Figure 2 shows the profile of the respondents based on their educational attainment. However, 22 observations were not counted. Most respondents are at the elementary level, Grade 6, in particular, and the majority of them were inside the computer shop for gaming rather than for academic purposes, as shown in Figures 8

and 9. The results of various studies showed that prolonged stay in Internet cafés because of computer gaming leads to computer addiction, which has negative effects on the academic performances of students. Thus, the result shown in Figure 2 is alarming, especially that the good foundation of education starts in the early years of a child's education that lay the groundwork for their future life and love of learning. A unstable basis may disrupt their belief in learning, but a solid foundation will put them on track to reach their maximum learning potential, according to Almon & Miller (2009). Therefore, good early learnings or education is significant to the children because they are believed to be the future and the vital resource of our nation. As such, children should acquire a good education in their early years if we are to create a nation that is focused on having citizens who can participate in nation-building. Meanwhile, poor elementary education may lead to the development of bad habits and behaviors as well as poor study habits, which would lead to poor academic performance and, consequently, to high levels of illiteracy.

Figure 3

In Figure 3, most of the persons-in-charge in Internet cafés observed are administrators or tagapamahala (51 out of 93 or 55%). Meanwhile, the remaining percentage of 45% are may-ari (42 out of 93).

Level of Implementation of the City Ordinance

Regarding the implementation of the City Ordinance, various indicators, based on the prohibitions indicated in the City Ordinance, were observed, such as (1) gambling exists inside the Internet cafés, (2) students wearing uniforms and visit during school hours are prohibited inside the Internet cafés, and (3) Internet users below 18 years old are not allowed to enter the computer shops during curfew hours.

Figure 4

Figure 4 shows the percentage distribution of Internet cafés according to the presence of gambling (i.e., betting on online games such as Defense of the Ancients (DOTA) and League of Legends (LOL)). Although the difference is minimal, 55% (51 out of 93) of these Internet cafés do not allow gambling. However, gambling was observed in the remaining 45% (42 out of 93).

Figure 5

When Internet café users were observed during data collection, 56% (423 out of 751) of them were wearing school uniforms, while a smaller percentage of 44% (328 out of 751) were not. These are all shown in Figure 5. However, 21 observations were not counted.

Figure 6

In terms of entering computer shops during school hours in Figure 6, 61% (456 out of 750) of them said they enter computer shops during school hours, while only 39% (294 out of 750) do not enter the computer shops during school hours. However, 22 observations were not counted.

Figure 7

During the curfew hour, which is 10:00 PM, Figure 7 shows that 65% (486 out of 751) of Internet café users observed said that they do not enter computer shops during curfew hours, while the other 35% (265 out of 751) enters computer shop during curfew hours. Moreover, 34% (254 out of 265) of the Internet café users who enter during curfew hours are of minor age, i.e., ages 10–17 years old. However, 21 observations were not counted.

During the study, observations that were deemed not applicable for the study, i.e., observations from participants who are not students and/or not minors, were not included. These include observations from “whether Internet café users entered Internet café in school uniform” shown in Figure 5, “whether Internet café users

entered Internet café during school hours” shown in Figure 6, and “whether Internet café users entered Internet café during curfew hours” shown in Figure 7.

Figure 8

Figure 8 shows the percentage distribution of Internet café users who enter computer shops while wearing uniforms according to whether they do research or not during their visit. It shows that 98% (414 out of 423) of the respondents were not there to do research; only 2% (9 out of 423) had this objective.

Figure 9

Figure 9 shows that only 3% (12 out of 455) of the respondents are doing research when they enter computer shops during school hours. The other 97% (443 out of 455) are doing other things. However, one observation is not counted.

The level of compliance/implementation by Internet café operators can be seen in Figures 4–9, clearly demonstrating that the prohibitions indicated in the City Ordinance were not implemented by the Internet café operators in their Internet cafés. During the survey, gambling was observed inside the Internet cafés, and students wearing school uniforms and visit during school hours were allowed to enter the computer shops. In addition, it was found out that these students entered computer shops, not for academics but other purposes, i.e., online gaming and other activities for their pleasure, and only 2% of them did research for academics. Furthermore, among those who entered computer shops during school hours, only 3% of them did research for academics.

As discussed above and as shown in Figures 8 and 9, a large number of participants are students who enter computer shops while in school uniform and during school hours, but they were not doing research or activities for their academics. Instead, they were playing online games during the survey. As discussed in Chapter 3, these respondents were hesitant to answer the survey questions at first because they obviously did not want to be disrupted with their games. As such, the researcher offered to shoulder the payment of the two-hour rent for the computer used by Internet café users during the survey as a way of convincing them to cooperate for the interview. This made them cooperate and answer the survey questions.

Although many of the study's participants were students, they rarely used the Internet café for academic purposes. The results showed that the majority of the participants, although they entered Internet cafés wearing uniforms and during school hours, were not doing research for their studies or for acquiring further knowledge that could help them improve their academic performance. The findings supported prior research (e.g., Gurol and Servindik, 2007; Furuholt, Kristiansen, and Wahid, 2008) showing Internet cafés are mostly used for entertainment, email, and chat. During the study, the students are expected to be doing activities related to their studies because they entered the Internet cafés wearing school uniforms and during school hours. However, they are found to be into online gaming. The reason could be that Internet café users are not aware of the City Ordinance. All respondents (Internet users) were found to be not aware of the City Ordinance nor any ordinance regulating the operation of computer shops / Internet cafés in the City. It was also obvious in their reactions that the City Ordinance is totally new to their ears. On the other hand, it could also be because the Internet café operators are

also not aware of the City Ordinance, or maybe some are aware but did not understand its provisions, which is the reason they are not implementing it. While it could be true that the barangay officials are constantly reminding the Internet café users of the prohibitions in the City Ordinance as they claimed, it still did not increase the level of awareness among Internet café operators because it was not properly/effectively communicated to them.

Level of Awareness

Figure 10

Figure 10 shows the percentage distribution of 93 Internet café persons-in-charge. During the survey, it was expected that the owners of the Internet cafés are more knowledgeable with the City Ordinance, considering that they are the ones dealing with the authorities in the process of their application for a business license. However, it was discovered that their level of knowledge or awareness on the City Ordinance is just the same as that of the mere administrators of the Internet cafés.

Out of 93 respondents (Internet café owners and administrators), only one is aware of the City Ordinance, while the rest were not aware. When they were asked about any other orders that they are aware of, 38% (35 out of 93) of them said that they do not know any city ordinance. The next 24% (22 out of 93) said that they do not know any city ordinance, but they are aware that there are some ordered restrictions. One restriction that the 20% (19 out of 93) of them said is the restriction of minors (18 years and below) inside computer shops beyond some specified time, which is usually 10:00 PM. Other restrictions and orders according to their responses are shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11

Figure 11 shows the responses of the Internet café owners and administrators when asked whether they know about the City Ordinance. The restrictions they mentioned are just some of the restrictions provided in the City Ordinance that they learned from the barangay officials. During the survey, it was observed that the

Internet Café operators/administrators are obviously unaware of the City Ordinance or any ordinance in the City that regulates the operation of Internet cafés. They even asked, “Ano ba ‘yang ordinance na yan? Ano ba ang maitutulong nyan sa negosyo namin?”

Responses from Parents

As mentioned in the preceding chapter, a separate survey was conducted involving the parents of children who frequently visit Internet cafés. Parents were interviewed in the study to ask about their children who are into computer games and conduct prolonged visits inside computer shops or Internet cafés. All of them (50 out of 50) said that the common objective of their children when going to computer shops is to play computer games. Seventeen out of 50 or 34%, aside from playing, were also said to be visiting computer shops to research or to accomplish assignments. This information can be seen in Figure 12.

Figure 12

Figure 13

Figure 14

Figures 13 and 14 show data of the frequency and duration of visits, in which 94% (47 out of 50) of the parents said that their children visit computer shops every day. In addition, most of them (44% or 22 out of 50) visit computer shops for about five to six hours. However, there were multiple responses per respondent.

Figure 15

Figure 15 shows the most common problems encountered by the 50 parent respondents. Among their responses, frequent absences in class appeared to be a general problem followed by dropping out to stop schooling and frequent skips in classes.

The common problems of parents could be contributed by the results in Figures 12, 13, and 14. As shown in Figure 12, the usual objective of the students in visiting Internet cafés is playing computer games. As to the frequency of visits, Figure 13 shows that 47 out of 50 parents said their children visit computer shops every day, while Figure 14 shows that parents said that their children stay at computers for five to six hours. Therefore, students visiting computer shops every day for online gaming for five to six hours will result in frequent absences from class, and worst, dropping out of school because, obviously, they would not have time to do their school work.

The result of the survey showed that the common objective of the children of all 50 respondents when going to computer shops is to play computer games. Only

17 out of 50 or 34% said that aside from playing games, their children are also visiting computer shops to do research or assignments. In terms of the frequency and duration of visits, 94% or 47 out of 50 parents said that their children visit computer shops every day. Most of them, 44% or 22 out of 50, visit computer shops for about five to six hours. In terms of the problems encountered by parents with their children, their most frequent problems are those involving lack of sleep because of the prolonged duration of playing games in computer shops. Moreover, their children were always absent for the same reason as addiction to playing games. Some of their children already stopped studying and were caught in bad company with their peers. They also reported that their children missed classes because of the prolonged stay in computer shops overnight, which resulted in poor scholastic grades. Teachers also reported to the parents that their children skipped some of their classes just to visit computer shops. Other problems include theft just to support the addiction to computer games and disrespect to parents, such as talking back to them and lying to cover up for missed classes when they sacrifice school for computer gaming.

The results of the survey showed that the prolonged duration of playing in computer shops resulted in a lack of sleep, leading to absences and missed classes. This condition, if ignored, will definitely result in poor education. Lack of education is the root cause of poverty, as claimed by Bryan Hickman (2015), because people with poor education cannot get high-paying jobs and, worst, some can even hardly get a job. Thus, unemployment and poverty are just two of the social problems stemmed from poor education that could result in more serious social problems. In addition, unemployment could result to poverty, which is the basic cause of all social evils, such as corruption, discrimination, etc., as well as other social problems, including

poor health, dependent children, and family instability, as well as other social problems confronting our society today.

The results of the survey clearly demonstrate the existence of Internet café-related problems in the City. Therefore, these should be perceived by influential personalities or by a large group of citizens as negative conditions so that City Officials would address them properly. Otherwise, this condition might exacerbate and result in more complicated societal problems.

The City's Information Dissemination of the City Ordinance

Section 14 of the City Ordinance states that the Implementing Agencies of the City Ordinance are the Philippine National Police (PNP) – LGU concerned, the barangay governments in coordination with the Business Permit and Licensing Office (BPLO), the engineering department, the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD) – LGU concerned, and the Department of Education (DepEd) – LGU concerned. The researcher went to each of the implementing agencies and asked how they disseminated the information on the City Ordinance. They all pointed to the Office of the City Council, where the City Ordinance originates. The researcher then went there to inquire how they disseminated the information on the City Ordinance. According to the Office Secretary of the City Council, “Ibinaba na namin ang pag disseminate ng information sa mga barangays. Nagbigay kami ng copies sa lahat ng barangays and advised them to implement it in their respective barangays.” The researcher continued to ask, “How about sa mga schools dito sa City, may ibinigay ba kayong memorandum or any document advising them to implement the City Ordinance?” The Secretary replied, “Ah, wala.” The researcher then went to the 13 barangays that are the subjects of this study. The resource persons of five

barangays were the barangay administrators, while the resource persons of the other eight barangays were the barangay secretaries. The researcher asked the following questions to the resource persons of 13 barangays:

1. "Pa'no nyo ikinalat o ipinaalam sa mga tao dito sa barangay nyo ang impormasyon patungkol sa City Ordinance?"
2. "Meron ba kayong strategy na ginawa o sinusunod sa pagkalat ng impormasyon patungkol sa City Ordinance?"

The following were the responses of the resource persons of the 13 barangays:

Barangay I: "Binibigyan namin ng kopya ng City Ordinance ang mga nag-a-apply ng barangay permit. Mino-monitor namin ang mga computer shop kung sumusunod ba sila sa City Ordinance."

Barangay II: "Nagbibigay lang kami ng kopya ng City Ordinance dun sa mga nag-a-apply ng barangay permit para sa Computer Shop. Nagmo-monitor kami lagi kung sinusunod ba nila yung mga ipinagbabawal ng City Ordinance."

Barangay III: "Binibigyan namin ng kopya ang mga nag-a-apply ng barangay permit para sa computer shop. Wala naman kaming strategy or what. Basta our barangay officials are doing surprise visit[s] to the computer shops from time to time."

Barangay IV: "Binibigyan namin ng kopya ang mga computer shop owner. Nag-susurprise visit ang mga barangay tanod namin sa mga computer shops kung talagang sinusunod nila yung mga bawal."

Barangay V: “Nagpo-provide kami ng copy ng City Ordinance sa mga applicant for barangay permit for computer shops. Mino-monitor namin ang mga computer shops para siguraduhin na sinusunod nila ang mga pinagbabawal sa City Ordinance.”

Barangay VI: “May binibigay kaming kopya sa mga applicant for barangay permit for computer shop o Internet café. Nagre-remind lagi ang mga barangay officials namin sa mga computer shops owner tungkol sa mga ipinagbabawal ng City Ordinance.”

Barangay VII: “Binibigyan namin ng kopya ng City Ordinance ang mga nag-a-apply ng barangay permit for computer shops o Internet cafés. Ang mga barangay tanod namin nag-i-inspect from time to time sa mga Internet café to make sure na hindi lumalabag ang mga owners sa City Ordinance.”

Barangay VIII: “Once na nag-apply sila (computer shop owners) ng barangay permit for Internet café, ini-inform namin sila sa mga ipinagbabawal sa City Ordinance at nagbibigay kami ng kopya. Regular nagtsi-check ang mga barangay officials namin para siguraduhin na sumusunod sila sa mga nakalagay sa City Ordinance.”

Barangay IX: “Binibigyan namin ang mga computer shop owners ng kopya ng City Ordinance at sinasabi namin na basahin nila para malaman nila ang mga ipinagbabawal. Wala kaming strategy para ipaalam sa mga tao ang City Ordinance pero patuloy naming mino-monitor ang mga computer shops para masiguro na sinusunod nila ang mga bawal.”

Barangay X: “Nagbibigay kami ng kopya ng City Ordinance sa mga nag-a-apply ng barangay permit at ipinapaliwanag namin kung anong mga nakasulat dun. Ang mga tanod namin, regular nagtsi-check sa mga computer shops kung may mga lumabag ba sa mga bawal na nakalagay sa City Ordinance.”

Barangay XI: “May binibigay kaming kopya ng City Ordinance ‘pag may nag-a-apply dito ng barangay permit para sa computer shops o Internet cafés. Mino-monitor ng mga tanod namin ang mga computer shops dito kasi baka yung iba hindi sinusunod ang mga nakalagay sa City Ordinance.”

Barangay XII: “Binibigyan namin ng kopya ang mga computer shop owners once na nag-a-apply sila ng barangay business permit. Nag-su-surprise check ang mga tanod namin sa mga computer shops / Internet cafés para siguraduhin na sinusunod nila ang mga nakalagay sa City Ordinance.”

Barangay XIII: “May kopya ng City Ordinance kaming binibigay sa mga nag-a-apply ng barangay business permit para sa computer shops o Internet cafés. Wala kaming ibang ginagawa sa pag disseminate ng information tungkol sa City Ordinance pero sinisiguro namin na walang nag-va-violate sa City Ordinance kaya regular ang mga tanod namin sa pagtsi-check.”

Based on the above responses of 13 barangays, it is obvious that all of them were doing the same procedures in disseminating the City Ordinance—furnishing copies of the City Ordinance to the Internet café operators.

Chapter V

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary

The case of the City Ordinance, which is the subject of this study, is no different from other government regulations / public policies that failed, such as the Energy-Efficient Homes Package in Australia, Ethanol Subsidies and Mandates, Building the Education Revolution initiated by Rudd Government in Australia, Rescission of the East–West Link Contract in Victoria, David Cameron’s Big Society in the United Kingdom, China’s One-Child Policy, the National Recovery Administration in the United States (McLaughlin, 2016), and other unsuccessful government programs and policies around the world.

There are various causes of program/policy failures identified by researchers during the implementation stage, and these include, but are not limited to, the lack of skills or competencies among the implementers, inadequate funding, a lack of dedication and perseverance over time, a lack of authority to reach the appropriate level of coordination, and most importantly, poor communication and consultation. These are just among the causes of policy failures identified by the researchers, but the lack of direction and poorly designed policies are also common causes of policy failure. Unfortunately, some government officials formulate policies for political reasons, such as heightening their political reputation to the public, which could be the reason for poorly designed public policies.

The City Ordinance was formulated as the City’s response to the proliferation of Internet cafés / computer shops, promoting Internet-related problems in the City and putting emphasis on the academic performance of minors/students and lead,

which could be jeopardized because of computer gaming. However, the City Council acknowledged that the operation and growth of these establishments have inadequately and largely uncontrolled, resulting in pornography and Internet-related problems. As such, the City Ordinance obviously did not serve its purpose because the results of the study showed that Internet café operators and users continuously violate the prohibited acts stipulated in the City Ordinance.

The results of the study suggest that the implementation of the City Ordinance lacks proper direction and commitment from the implementers or the City Officials. It was clearly stipulated in the City Ordinance that the implementing agencies are the City's PNP and the barangay governments, in coordination with BPLO, the engineering department, DSWD, and DepEd. In Section 10 of the City Ordinance, it was stipulated that the inspection team, composed of representatives from PNP and BPLO, shall conduct a regular inspection with the Internet café / computer gaming shops to ensure compliance with the City Ordinance. However, the result shows that the barangay officials (particularly the "tanod") are the ones conducting the inspection, and not on a regular basis. The implementation of the City Ordinance has obviously been so lax that the stipulations indicated therein as to the implementation are not being followed.

While it can be said that the City Ordinance has been communicated to the Internet café operators, the communication did not include participatory processes. Instead, the barangay simply passes information through furnishing the copies of the City Ordinance to Internet café operators upon their application of the barangay permit. However, whether the Internet café operators have read and understood the City Ordinance provided to them is a question that can be answered through the

result of this study. As such, the results of this study show that only 1% of the respondents (Internet café operators) is aware of the City Ordinance. The rest mentioned the restrictions from the barangay, but they do not know about the City Ordinance. The barangay officials are imposing some of the prohibitions stipulated in City Ordinance but are not explaining to the Internet café operators the City Ordinance that prohibits them from doing so.

Laws are sometimes effective because they are backed up by the possibility of severe enforcement, prompting individuals to weigh risk and reward before engaging in a banned behavior. Accordingly, typical economic analysis is based on the assumption that if the expected cost of conduct—consisting of the severity and likelihood of punishment—exceeds the expected benefit, the actor will refrain from engaging in that behavior, according to Becker (1968). Indeed, typical economic analysis assumes that issues about the effect of the law on human conduct begin and end with the assumption that behavior reacts to rewards and punishments. As such, community members who believe the law is unjust are less likely to follow it, according to Mullen and Nadler 2008; Nadler (2005). The government can communicate the law or public policy to the people in a variety of methods, but the finest communication is the ability to provide information, make one's voice known, and engage in discussions and debates. However, what the barangay officials did was merely imposing to Internet café operators the compliance of the desired behavior rather than persuading them to do the desired behavior through participative communication processes. Unfortunately, the government's traditional way of communicating the policies and programs to the public still continues amid the advent of the new technology, such as formulating and disseminating the policy through written instruments without consulting the affected or target citizens. It's

unfortunate that the target audience, the Internet café operators and users, especially the students, are not aware that there exists a City Ordinance that concerns them. The results of the survey on the dissemination efforts done on the City Ordinance show that the barangays assume that the Internet café operators will comply with the City Ordinance by just giving them copies of the same. However, the dissemination done by the barangays on the City Ordinance is not surprising. It has been the normal practice in the Philippines and the government's traditional way of communicating to the public that campaigns to mitigate societal or environmental problems or regarding programs/initiatives to improve the lives of the citizens are being done through disseminating or circulating copies of the written laws/regulations/programs to the concerned citizens, then proceeds to impose the law or regulation. The policymakers normally do not follow up on the efficacy of the policy they formulated, and apply or practice the two-way process of communication in disseminating such a policy.

With the advent of new technology, government officials or policymakers should veer away from the traditional way of communicating to their people and rather make use of the contemporary communications today that could easily reach and persuade the people. In addition, policymakers and other government officials should have realized for the longest time that there is no one-size-fits-all in communicating policies. Communicating policies vary widely among locales and other stakeholders involved, by platform and channel, and dependent on the message to convey or send and the receiver of the message. Thus, the barangays' dissemination of the City Ordinance by simply providing copies to Internet café operators upon the application and renewal of their business permit is definitely not effective. Furthermore, the barangay officials' enforcement of the prohibited acts

without instilling in them (the Internet café operators) the importance of their cooperation in abiding the City Ordinance and the effect of not abiding it cannot guarantee a sustained desired behavior. It may sound too idealistic and require big funds, but the most efficient way of interacting/communicating with the public is by involving them and letting them participate in the discussion. This way, they are able to have a better grasp of the programs or policies that are formulated to mitigate societal or environmental problems. Communication should be at the center of any development or program policy, but engaging the people concerned should be regarded as equally important.

Some scholars say that when local stakeholders are not involved from the start of an intervention, the chances of issues and failures increase considerably. There are numerous examples of communication failing to accomplish desired results due to people's initial lack of involvement or their inadequate or contradictory comprehension of concerns by various stakeholders. Those specific behavioural changes cannot be done without wider social approval, and/or changes are becoming more widely recognized, according to Thomas Tufte and Paolo Mefalopulos (2009).

Conclusion

The City Ordinance was formulated and passed to regulate the operation of Internet café operations in the City. However, it was observed that the Internet café operators do not behave in ways that are consistent with the objective of the City Ordinance. Moreover, the City is not isolated from the widespread cases of parents who have serious concerns over their children who frequently visit Internet cafés. Although lacking documentation, cases of parents complaining about the poor

academic performance of their children and school dropouts because of playing games in Internet cafés have been often heard and seemed to have become a normal issue among parents today. However, to substantiate that such cases really exist in the City, which could also broaden the significance of this study, the survey was conducted to 50 selected parents with children who frequently visit Internet cafés as the respondents. Based on the responses of the parents, the top reason of their children in going to the Internet cafés is playing computer games (Figure 12), and this can be corroborated with the result of the survey with the Internet users as shown in Figure 9, which showed that only 3% were doing research and 97% were doing other things, such as playing computer games, while inside Internet cafés during school hours. As to the frequency of their children's visit to the Internet cafés, the top responses of the parents were their children visit Internet cafés every day and for the duration of about five to six hours (Figures 13 and 14). The result of the survey as to the frequency of their children's visit in the Internet cafés and the result of the survey with Internet café users, wherein the majority of the samples or 61% of them entered Internet cafés during school hours and 65% of them entered Internet cafés during curfew hours, are suggestive of the children's academic problems. These results corroborate with the result of the survey with the parents (Figure 15) wherein the most common problems encountered by parents were "madalas absent sa klase," "tumigil sa pag-aaral," and "madalas skip sa klase." The most common problems encountered by these parents with their children, if ignored, may degenerate serious societal problems and, consequently, may affect the economic conditions in the City. Therefore, it was deemed necessary to examine the extent of the dissemination and implementation of City Ordinance considering that the said ordinance specifically addressed the urgent need to regulate and check the entry of

minors/students to Internet cafés or computer gaming shops as excessive playing especially that during school hours is a distraction that can jeopardize their academic performance and advancement. The strategy used in disseminating the information about the City Ordinance was examined to understand how and up to what extent the dissemination and implementation of the City Ordinance were being done and why the Internet café operators continued to violate the prohibitions provided in the said ordinance. This way, flaws in the dissemination and implementation process of the City Ordinance may be realized or identified, leading to a more stringent implementation of the said ordinance and, consequently, lead to the alleviation of the dilemma that parents in the City are experiencing with their children. However, the results of the survey conducted with the barangays show that they are doing the same thing in the dissemination of the City Ordinance. They just provide copies of the City Ordinance to Internet café operators upon the application or renewal of the business permit. The strategy used in disseminating City Ordinance is suggestive of the results of the survey on awareness and implementation.

The implementation by Internet café operators and their awareness of the City Ordinance were examined through various indicators based on the prohibited acts provided in the said city ordinance.

The result of the survey on the awareness showed that 99% of the respondents who are Internet café owners and administrators are not aware of the City Ordinance. Instead, they talked about the restrictions imposed by their respective barangay officials when asked if they know about the City Ordinance or any ordinance that regulates the operation of Internet cafés in the City. Most of the restrictions they mentioned (shown in Figure 11) were “bawal and 18 years old

pababa” on curfew hours, “bawal ang naka-uniform,” “bawal ang naka-hubad,” “bawal ang alak o pag-iinom sa loob,” and “bawal ang pustahan.” The responses of the respondents are suggestive of poor information dissemination of the City Ordinance.

The result of the survey on the implementation of the City Ordinance showed that the prohibited acts, as provided in the said ordinance, were still present in the Internet cafés. Gambling was still observed in 45% of the surveyed Internet cafés. Students are still allowed to enter computer shops even when they are wearing school uniforms during school hours and even if they 18 years old below who visit during curfew hours. Internet café operators and administrators continued to do the prohibited acts in the City Ordinance, considering that they already knew these restrictions as imposed by their barangay officials, which they mentioned during the survey. As such, these acts of the Internet café operators and administrators are suggestive of poor implementation of the City Ordinance by the City Officials, which could be a result of poor or improper information dissemination or insufficient information campaigns of the said ordinance. Public information campaign requires effective communication between citizens and government. Thus, this study acknowledged the views of the scholars that information campaigns alone will not influence the behavior of a huge number of individuals on a long-term basis, and that the persuasion theory's concept that exposure to knowledge causes a change in attitude, which causes a change in conduct was not supported by empirical evidence. The researcher strongly believes, however, that there is no other effective way of disseminating the information of any program policies except through effective communication. This could only be possible if we will embrace the opportunities brought about by the advent of the new technology.

Recommendations

“One of the great mistakes is to judge policies and programs by their intentions rather than their results.” — Milton Friedman

Public policies and programs are typically formulated as the government's response to societal problems and its effort for the betterment of society. In the Philippines, solving the problem is the intention of government officials when making the policy, but whether the results of such policy are carefully thought of is a question in which the answer is obviously “no” based on how public policies are being disseminated. As such, policymakers and government officials must keep up with the technological change pace in the realm of communication today rather than living in the government's traditional way of disseminating the policy and programs, such as formulating and promulgating the public policy and disseminating it to the public through mass media, and making copies available through the Internet or the designated government agencies or distribute printed copies to the public without consulting them and evaluating its efficacy based on the results.

Giving people knowledge is only one aspect of the communication required to influence social views and individual action. The communication process must be far more than merely informing individuals that something is happening. Today's development thinking must increasingly recognize the link between participatory communication and empowerment—that is, enhanced individual and community perception of capacity to manage their lives and effect change. People learn more effectively and adopt new ideas as their own when they learn from their peers and can respond and engage in discourse, as opposed to passively receiving information from the media or authority. People's behavior is more likely to change if they are

more actively participating in the process rather than just passive recipients of messages, because discussion is more effective than listening. Furthermore, allowing a larger number of people to talk, engage, and reply to one another ultimately equips them to accept political responsibility, which is a critical component of achieving large and long-term change, according to Warnock and Wilson (2007).

The Latin root of the word “communication” is *communicare*, which means “to share.” As such, we communicate to share our point of view, and this is a core human trait within and between families, friends, colleagues, and strangers at every level in society. Those we speak to may, or may not, be persuadable. However, if both sides are listening to each other—that is, “sharing” the discussion—a dialogue ensues, resulting in agreement, or an agreement to differ, or unresolved opposition, or conflict (Warnock and Wilson, 2007).

Communication is also at the center of social networks and social movements. Social movements rely on interpersonal connection, associations, and information to bring people together and effectively advocate to magnify the voices of the disadvantaged, according to Vincent, (2009). For example, the very successful Treatment Action Campaign in South Africa used advocacy, mass mobilization, and political pressure to modify the South African government's antiretroviral (ARV) medicine regulations, according to Panos London Report (2006).

Indeed, one-way communication has proven to be ineffective in many ways and in many instances, especially with the environment of the information that has been changed and keeps on changing and with the challenges in the following areas. First, in an age of information overload, the old way of government's communicating or reaching to the public is no longer effective. Second, as People

prefer short, brief, and easy-to-understand information (ideally in image format), therefore they are less inclined to read lengthy and dispassionate government texts and hence are unlikely to understand policy specifics. Third, traditional government communication of public policy is ineffective in appealing to citizens to participate in the policy because it is not intended to create a favorable impression of the policy or induce citizens to participate, but rather to inform citizens of the objective facts and rationale of the policy.

In our changing information environment, there should be a fundamental shift in the way citizens and the government communicate, toward more active outreach and advertising of programs. As mentioned in the previous chapter, the condition of information overload has made people choose condensed instead of long, detailed, and verbose information. In visual communication, the presenter usually condensed and compressed information or message to convey to the audience (McLuhan & Gordon, 2003). This way, the audience can easily understand the message being conveyed. Therefore, the use of visual communication is increasing as it speeds up information processing. Furthermore, additional visual communication aspects should be introduced into government communication in order to generate a positive impression and image of government policy. In the current information world, the effectiveness of policy communication will continue to deteriorate if the government will not shift to the modern way of communicating its people who may increasingly disregard government policies. While it could be true that stringent implementation would be done, such as penalizing those who will not comply with the policy, such compliance will not be sustainable. Thus, the efficacy of the public policy will just be temporary because the citizens' compliance is just to avoid being penalized, but the behavior change is not sustainable.

The dissemination done on City Ordinance is suggestive of the opinion that the barangays' efforts to alleviate Internet café-related problems were in vain. Therefore, the City should recognize and consider initiatives that promote participatory communication that allow individuals to express themselves, discover common concerns, and seek answers from within their community. In addition, people concerned should be involved in the planning and implementation of development activities which would give them a sense of ownership rather than just passive receivers of decisions or interventions made by the government.

Communities should be encouraged to participate in program planning, implementation, and assessment. This would provide people a sense of involvement in their lives and communities, as well as a sense of ownership and skills that they could utilize beyond the timetable of development programs, according to Kavinya, Alam & Decock (1994). One of the most important contributions of participatory theories to development communication has been community empowerment. However, empowerment is only feasible if community members critically reflect on their experiences and grasp the causes for intervention failure and success, according to Bradford & Gwynne (1995); Purdey, Adhikari, for failure and Robinson & Cox, (1994).

Technological advances have brought unlimited opportunities, which our government can take advantage of in engaging participatory communication. The participatory communication paradigm does not advocate for the replacement of essential communication functions connected with information transmission, but rather expands its scope to encompass more engaging modes of communication.

This can take many different forms, such as drama, dance, storytelling, or interpersonal dialogue–based activities. As such, to reach a wider audience, the City may record drama performances by community troupes, host group discussion sessions following video screenings or radio broadcasts, or use roleplay tactics in peer education and training initiatives. In addition, to encourage person-to-person dialogue and group mobilization, the City may use interactive media platforms. It may also use electronic and digital technology in ways that allow for widespread, even worldwide distribution, such as entertainment-education.

According to Singhal and Rogers (1999), the term "entertainment-education" refers to a communication approach for disseminating information through the media that has the potential for worldwide distribution. It is defined as "the deliberate design and implementation of a media message to entertain and educate, with the goal of increasing the knowledge of audience regarding educational concerns, creating desirable attitudes, and changing overt behavior. It is focused with social change at the individual and community levels, similar to social marketing and health promotion, and focuses on how entertainment media like music, soap operas, cartoons, etc. can be utilized to transmit or share knowledge that leads to pro-social behavior.

An awareness campaign on the City Ordinance should be done through the aforementioned different forms of participatory communication and should not just be concentrated on Internet café operators but rather all citizens in the City. With the birth of social platforms, it would be easier for the City Officials to reach their citizens. A such, social media, being the game changer in almost everything that surrounds us, would be very beneficial to this endeavor. Social media sites, such as Facebook,

Twitter, and YouTube, have been proven as effective communication platforms in many ways and in various instances. One prominent example is the remarkable Million People March at Luneta, which was spurred by public outrage over the Priority Development Assistance Fund scam, called for the absolute abolition of the Pork Barrel fund. Initial calls for this demonstration spread on social media, mostly on Facebook and Twitter, with the goal of holding a protest on August 26, 2013, at Luneta Park in Manila, as well as other locations across the country. According to some media critics, this was the first-ever major gathering in the Philippines that was called and organized mostly using social media networks.

Facebook, with more than 2 billion monthly active users worldwide, according to the article by Josh Constine at TechCrunch (2017), comprises the largest blend of demographics of any social platform. According to the said article, YouTube has also been a popular and effective way of connecting to people. Its growth reflects the shift toward more convenient visual communication, with 4 billion videos seen every day and 800 million users per month (YouTube, 2012). Twitter, on the other hand, is also a social platform widely used today, especially by the millennials. Thus, images indeed stand out in communication compared to text.

The aforementioned instance and discussion show the persuasiveness and effectiveness of social media platforms in disseminating the information. Therefore, the City Officials should leverage these platforms in which most people today, especially the young ones, spent so much of their time. Various ways of communication in contemporary times undoubtedly bring great advantage to our government officials to effectively communicate public policies to citizens. However, this needs the required skill, funding support, and commitment from the City Officials

because, as some scholars say, exposure to information alone is not effective in changing the behavior rather, it should be strategically communicated to the citizens.

For the awareness campaign, the City officials can make smart and successful use of "edutainment," in which information about City Ordinances and debates about Internet addiction, which leads to complicated social difficulties, are integrated in enticing music or dramatic tales performed out by entertaining actors. These could be posted on Facebook, YouTube, and on digital boards in public places. A well-known example of the successful use of edutainment was a long-running and successful radio and television drama series that reaches 70% of South Africa's population and covers problems like as HIV & AIDS, health, and interpersonal relationships. According to research, it has significantly reduced HIV and AIDS-related stigma in the country. Research strongly suggests that it has reduced HIV and AIDS-related stigma in the country. In all their awareness campaign efforts, the City Officials should devise their concept strategically that it will not only promote awareness on the public that there exists a city ordinance, which addresses the prevalence of the Internet addiction among young children especially the students, but should be something that can persuade the citizens especially the parents to do their fair share in educating their children about the adverse effect of Internet addiction to their lives and also explaining the prohibitions of the City Ordinance. The awareness campaign should contain a message that emphasizes the adverse effects of Internet addiction and that the immensity of this problem is already present in the City, but there exists a City Ordinance to address this problem. In all these recommended efforts, Internet café operators, parents, and young ones (elementary and high school students) should be engaged and empowered, thus applying the participatory communication process. The school

teachers should also actively participate in all these endeavors because they play a great role in developing the attitude and future of their students. During the empowerment efforts, various activities involving the family members should be considered, such as recreational and sports activities promoting the closeness of family members, and other activities such as a talent show or competition for the young ones. Such activities could be the focus of the young ones, dissuading their interest from playing online games.

The implementation stage is very important as well in all policy programs because, as previously mentioned, the success of a policy is contingent on the success of the implementation. As such, strategic communication plays a great role during the implementation stage. During the implementation, Internet café operators should be encouraged to understand the consequence of violating the prohibitions of the City Ordinance and the corresponding incentives when they religiously comply with it. In addition, the City Officials should not just inflict on the minds of Internet café operators the penalty as a consequence should they continuously violate the city ordinance, but rather the good contribution they could give the community as well if they will comply with the City Ordinance. Hence, It is critical that consultation be viewed as a continuous process rather than a one-time event. Moreover, continuous evaluation and monitoring of the compliance and implementation of the City Ordinance should be present.

Furthermore, the City Officials should consider revisiting the City Ordinance as well. Existing policies must also be modified to respond to a changing political, social, and economic context (Governance Cluster, 2014). In amending the City

Ordinance, the four key stages of Participatory Development (Thomas Tufte and Paolo Mefalopulos, 2009) discussed below should be considered.

1. **Research Stage** is where the development problem is precisely described. This procedure can be participated in by all relevant stakeholders. The study of previous experiences, individual and community knowledge and attitudes, existing policies, and other relevant contextual information linked to socioeconomic conditions, culture, spirituality, gender, and so on can all be included in development research.
2. **Design Stage** defined the actual actions. A participative approach ensures community ownership and commitment. Furthermore, active participation by local inhabitants and other stakeholders aims to improve the quality and relevance of the proposed solutions.
3. **Implementation Stage** is when the proposed intervention is put into action. Participation at this level boosts commitment, relevance, and long-term sustainability.
4. **Evaluation Stage** guarantees that the most significant changes are voiced, brought to the forefront of public attention, and evaluated. In order to conduct a meaningful evaluation, indicators and measurements should be defined in a participatory process involving all important stakeholders from the outset of the effort.

The City Officials must pay serious attention to the issue of internet addiction. The fact that the World Health Organization (WHO) has considered it as a mental illness, according to recent news, the City Officials should recognize that such a

problem exists in the City. Otherwise, this condition might just be continuously ignored until such time when people would realize that the problem has proliferated in the City and ruined the education and future of the young ones.

The aforementioned recommended efforts to address internet addiction, especially involving participatory approaches, are maybe too idealistic and undeniably require big funds and commitment from the City Officials, which means that they should allot their time regularly to do the needed tasks. However, if allotting their time and providing great funding support to the programs and initiatives would mean a better society, then the political leaders should not think twice. After all, they are being elected to the position to become the people's steward for a better society. Efforts in formulating any public policy will just turn futile and end up with a failed public policy without the support from political leaders from the start. In general, implementing agencies cannot be expected to shift to a new paradigm without political leaders' knowledge, support, and long-term commitment.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A

Barangay: _____

Pangalan ng Computer Shop / Internet Café (optional): _____

1. Ano ang katungkulan ninyo dito sa Internet café na ito?

_____ May-ari _____ Tagapamahala

2. Alam nyo ba ang City Ordinance No. 47?

_____ OO _____ HINDI

Kung OO, ano ang pagkaka-intindi nyo sa Ordinansa na ito? (Pakilarawan ang Ordinansa ayon sa inyong pagkakaintindi).

Kung HINDI, may alam ba kayong Ordinansa na ipinatutupad sa Taguig patungkol sa operasyon at pamamahala ng Internet café upang kontrolin o ipagbawal o limitahan ang mga ginagawa sa loob ng Internet café?

APPENDIX B

QUESTIONNAIRE FOR STUDENTS WHO VISIT THE SELECTED INTERNET CAFÉ

Barangay _____

Internet Café _____

Age _____

Grade _____

Sex _____

a. Do you enter the Internet café in school uniform?

_____ Yes _____ No

If yes, are you doing research/school work during these visits?

_____ Yes _____ No

b. Do you enter the Internet café during school hours?

_____ Yes _____ No

If yes, are you doing research/school work during these visits?

_____ Yes _____ No

c. Do you enter the Internet café during curfew hours?

_____ Yes _____ No

APPENDIX C

Ang hangarin ng Maikling Survey na ito ay upang matugunan ang problema ng mga magulang sa kanilang mga anak dulot ng paglalaro nila sa computer shops o Internet cafés. Pakisagutan ang mga sumusunod:

Name: _____

Address: _____

1. Nagpupunta ba ang anak nyo sa computer shops o Internet cafés?
_____ Oo _____ Hindi

2. Ano ang madalas na ginagawa ng anak nyo sa computer shops?
_____ Naglalaro ng computer games
_____ Nag-reresearch
_____ Gumagawa ng assignments
Others (please specify)

3. Gaano kadalas sa computer shops ang anak nyo?
_____ Araw-araw
_____ Tatlong beses sa isang linggo
_____ Limang beses sa isang linggo
Others (please specify)

4. Ilang oras namamalagi ang anak nyo sa computer shops o Internet cafés?
_____ 1–2 hrs.
_____ 3–4 hrs.
_____ 5–6 hrs.
_____ 7–8 hrs.
Others (please specify)

5. Ano ang naging problema nyo sa anak nyo sa paglalaro nito ng computer games sa computer shops?
_____ Tumigil sa pag-aaral
_____ Madalas absent sa klase
_____ Madalas nag-skip sa klase
Others (please specify)
